

Deliverable N°: D7.8
Deliverable Title: Report on the analysis of the existing standards
WP N°: 7
WP Leader: ASRO
WP Title: Value chain sustainability, socio-laboral inclusion and standardization
Delivery Date: 30 th of June 2024
Actual Date: 31 st of May 2024
Lead Beneficiary: Romanian Standards Body - ASRO
Contributing Beneficiaries: HOLOSS, IDENER, LVA, AWI, CTAQUA, CUT, IOLR, IT
Dissemination level: PU

DOCUMENT HISTORY

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SUMMARY

This report contains information about the activities developed during M9th and M14th of NOVAFOODIES project and the obtained results.

The interpretation of the data obtained, and the conclusions drawn are of importance for the standardization world in the area of the NOVAFOODIES project.

The report lays out the basis for the future Standardization Roadmap and sets the direction for the future developments in the standardization of the area encompassed by the NOVAFOODIES project.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ISO – the International Organization for Standardization

CEN – the European Committee for Standardization

WTO – World Trade Organization

SPS Agreement - Sanitary and Phytosanitary Agreement

TBT Agreement – Technical Barriers to Trade Agreement

TC – technical committee

CMO – Common Market Organization

SWD – Second staff working document

PECH – Committee of Fisheries

CFP – Common Fisheries Policy

GFSI - Global Food Safety Initiative

NDA – Nondisclosure agreement

FSMS – Food Safety Management Systems

CWA – CEN Workshop Agreement

1 STANDARDIZATION IN THE AREA OF FISHERIES AND AQUACULTURE

The existing formal standards in the NOVAFOODIES developed processes have been identified and analyzed, especially those within ISO/TCs and CEN/TCs.

In fisheries and aquaculture, the relevant standards and other documents related to definitions and terminology derive from:

- the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) Guide 2;

Standardization and related activities – General vocabulary (ISO, 2004);

- binding agreements of the WTO – the Agreement on the Application of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS Agreement), and the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT Agreement); and
- relevant food standards, guidelines and codes of practice issued by the Codex Alimentarius Commission (Codex, or CAC).

Standards and the certification systems sitting behind them, whether public or private, are a means of assuring buyers of the quality of products or the conformity of processes and production methods. Quality aspects can be related to the product itself or the process by which it was produced. Standards and certification are especially useful where there is information asymmetry, that is, where buyers and consumers cannot easily judge certain quality aspects of products or production processes.

In terms of content, standards can relate to products themselves (specifications or criteria for product attributes) or to processes (outlining criteria and practices for the way products are made). Food safety standards typically focus on process aspects with the overall goal of improving the safety of final products. However, they can also define product standards related to residues of additives, contaminants or in terms of microbiological criteria. Ecolabels focus on where fish and seafood come from and how they are harvested or farmed (and/or the impact of that harvest on related fauna and flora) rather than on aspects of the products themselves. Process standards might relate to performance criteria that establish verifiable requirements for the production process, or management criteria relating to documentation and monitoring.

The interpretation of the analysis made by the partners (derived from the information and identified gaps of existing standards or gaps in the EU/international standardization) will be later on used to develop a Roadmap for standardization in the project area, for proposing improvements and topics to existing and new standards.

1.1 Aquaculture in Europe

The strategy of the European Commission “Farm to Fork” addressed challenges associated with each step in the food chain and announced several legislative initiatives. One was a revision of marketing standards ‘to provide for the uptake and supply of sustainable agricultural, fisheries and aquaculture products’.

Marketing standards define quality characteristics and certain requirements for the product content and presentation. They apply to both EU and non-EU products placed on the EU's internal market. The draft action plan, annexed to the strategy, announced a revision of EU marketing standards for both agricultural and fishery & aquaculture products during 2021-2022. More specifically with regards to fishery and aquaculture, the Commission's amended 2020 work program, published on 27th May 2020, initially announced the revision for Q4 2020, including the objective to simplify the legal set-up by combining several regulations into one.

However, in its May 2021 Communication on the blue economy, the Commission announced its adoption for 2022. The proposal would allow for 'modern, sustainable marketing standards for seafood to provide comparable information to consumers and operators in the supply chain on the environmental and social sustainability of seafood and on its carbon footprint'.

The general objectives of the marketing standards are currently covered by Regulation 1379/2013 on the 'common organization of the markets in fishery and aquaculture products' (the CMO Regulation), while the standards as such are spelled out in three older Council regulations (Regulation 2406/96 for certain fishery products, Regulation 1536/92 for preserved tuna and bonito and Regulation 2136/89 for preserved sardines and sardine-type products).

The now more than 20 year old marketing standards were subject to an evaluation in 2018, concluded in the Commission staff working document SWD (2019)453. It outlined that the marketing standards have a positive but limited impact in terms of their objectives. Only a limited number of products are covered by the standards and there is a lack of criteria related to sustainability.

Ahead of the revision, the Commission launched an inception impact assessment followed by a public consultation (17th November 2020 – 23rd February 2021). Besides pointing to the previous evaluation, the introductory text to the public consultation referred to the fact that imports from non-EU countries that are not covered by EU standards have increased which is harming fair competition. It also noted there is a growing demand by consumers and operators to be better informed on sustainability aspects.

While there are a number of private sustainability schemes, there is no EU legal framework to regulate information on sustainability aspects specifically for seafood products and the revision of the marketing standards would be an opportunity to address this.

The Commission did not include a legislative proposal on a revision of marketing standards in its work programme for 2022. Instead, on 17th December 2021, the Commission launched an online questionnaire in view of the upcoming implementation report on the CMO Regulation (a legal obligation). All stakeholders, including the fishing industry, non-governmental organizations, academic, scientific, social, and economic partners were invited to take part in the online questionnaire and share their views by 14th March 2022.

The Commission finally published the implementation report on the CMO Regulation on 21st of February 2023, as part of a fisheries and oceans package, consisting of four communications: the two implementation reports (on the CMO Regulation and on the CFP Regulation) and two action plans in the light of the Green Deal. In the implementation report on the CMO Regulation, the

Commission takes stock of the implementation of the market policy, highlighting its achievements following its reform in 2013 (along with the reform of the CFP).

As far as marketing standards are concerned, the implementation report is rather brief. It summarized the above consultation activities and stated that the consultations confirmed the potential benefits of an EU consumer information framework on the sustainability of food products, including fishery products. It adds that, as announced in the Farm to Fork strategy, it is important to take forward the Sustainable Food System Initiative that the Commission intends to adopt in 2023.

The Commission presented the implementation report on the CMO Regulation at the PECH meeting on 1st of March 2023. In the presentation, Commission representatives noted that current consumer labelling and marketing standards do not fully contribute to raising consumer awareness of product sustainability. However, the upcoming Sustainable Food System Initiative would provide scope for better consumer information. This means that the Commission's aim to put forward a legislative proposal to revise the marketing standards (as announced in the Farm to Fork strategy) has not been achieved. Possibly new action, specifically for the seafood sector, might be announced once the 'horizontal' Sustainable Food System Initiative has been adopted. However, it is not listed in the Commission's work program for 2024 and it remains uncertain when this will be adopted.

Following the Commission's implementation report, the PECH Committee prepared an own-initiative report on the CMO Regulation. It was adopted in the PECH Committee on 29th of November 2023 and in plenary on 18th of January 2024. The resolution raises issues such as improving consumer information (e.g. on sustainability) and tackling mislabeling. With regard to marketing standards, it points out that the Commission's evaluation has identified shortcomings in achieving the objectives of the CMO, while also highlighting the need for better compliance and opportunities for simplification and modernization.[1]

On the Black Sea coast, Romania has an exclusive economic zone (area 25,000 km² and a coastline of 250 km). About 3% of the national area of Romania is covered by the hydrographic system, with over 843,710 ha. Natural areas with potential for the fisheries sector include: 400,000 ha of natural lakes (including the Danube Delta and 7 reservoirs), 84,500 ha of fish farms, 15,000 ha of nurseries, 66,000 km of rivers, of which 18,200 km in the mountain area and 1,075 km on the Danube River. Integration into the EU brought projects worth more than 730 million euros to the Romanian fishing sector, through the European funding programs: European Fisheries Fund (2007-2014), European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (2014-2020), and European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (2021-2027), correlated to the contribution of the Romanian Government.[2]

1.2 Standardization for food safety and quality in aquaculture

Many authors specified that further complicating the variety of public sector food safety regulations is the multitude of standards applied by the private sector. These relate to a range of objectives, including food safety and quality but also to animal health, environmental protection, and even social development, and are often linked to private firms' Corporate Social Responsibility strategies [3].

As noted before, a range of factors has fueled the trend towards safety and quality standards, at international and European levels, but in some cases also at national level. Food safety scares have weakened public confidence in governments' abilities to guarantee food safety, especially the safety of imported food.

Government policies related to product liability and due diligence as well as the shift towards more performance-based regulatory frameworks put the onus on private sector firms to assume responsibility for food safety management. Large food firms, especially retailers, have increasing bargaining power vis-à-vis other businesses in the supply chain, and are requiring suppliers to be certified.

Formal standards provide authorities and buyers with some insurance against food scares and a due diligence defense. Third-party certification offers buyers direct access to written audit reports and/or their results. In contrast, certification by competent authorities (government inspection agencies) and their compliance-conformity evaluations are targeted at providing assurance to other public control authorities, not individual private sector buyers. Publicly available results might only be presented in the aggregate to give assurance that the overall system is functioning well.

The increasing vertical integration and complexity of supply chains in fish and seafood also stimulate the growth of private standards, as B2B tools used in the context of direct procurement contracts, which are starting to replace the traditional structure of "importer–wholesaler–retailer". Complex value chains – where raw materials are potentially sourced globally, processed in a second country, and retailed in yet another – require sophisticated systems for ensuring traceability and guaranteeing that sanitary and hygiene standards are maintained at every stage of the value chain – from farm or boat to fork. These traceability and chain of custody systems are built into the frameworks included in most certification standards schemes.

There are many different private safety and quality standards applying to fisheries and aquaculture, including: private in-house standards (producers or processors manuals of standard operating procedures [SOPs]), buyer guidelines, collective private quality standards (codes of conduct or codes of practice) developed by local, regional, or national producer/industry groups; NGO-driven schemes; and national and international FSMSs.

The overview of the various types of standards are organized as follows:

- private in-house standards (guidelines) of large retail firms;
- formal standards (codes of conduct) developed by local, regional or international standardization organizations;
- NGO-driven schemes (mainly related to aquaculture); and
- National and international FSMSs (Food Safety Management Schemes).

Examples:

1. ISO Technical Committee ISO/TC 234, Fisheries and Aquaculture

In 2007, the International Organization for Standardization established Technical Committee ISO/TC 234, Fisheries and Aquaculture. The ISO/TC 234 focuses on areas where:

- performance can be assessed against specified benchmarks (e.g. under global sustainability market certification regimes);
- actors in the sector can learn from one another's experience, develop best practice, efficiently exchange knowledge and utilize international expertise in the field;
- food business operators can reduce workloads by avoiding conflicting documentation requirements and re-using data;
- electronic data interchange and automatic translation of product and process parameters can be enabled;
- there are global markets for equipment and technology, and sufficient similarity in operating conditions to warrant establishing minimum design, testing or performance standards;
- there is a desire for international transparency in import requirements used by various countries, in order to support fair trade; and
- comparability of data can be promoted.

The ISO/TC 234's activities in fisheries and aquaculture include the creation of:

- Working groups for dealing with:
 - traceability of fish products,
 - environmental monitoring of seabed impacts from marine finfish farms,
 - aquaculture technology,
 - food safety for aquaculture farms,
 - methodology for sea lice counts, and
 - calculation of "fish-in, fish-out" (FIFO) and feed conversion ratios (FCRs)
- Advisory group for dealing with:
 - aquaculture advisory group [4]

2. ISO 22000 was developed in 2005, building on previous food-safety-related standards, as an attempt to establish one internationally recognized standard for food safety management systems. To date, however, it sits alongside the range of other private and public schemes.

There has been some collaboration between the ISO and the GFSI (Global Food Safety Initiative). For example, the ISO participates in the GFSI Technical Committee. A comparison conducted by the GFSI of the GFSI Guidance Document and ISO 22000 showed strong similarities.

However, different approaches to accreditation and differences in ownership – retailer driven GFSI versus the diverse public/private ISO 22000 membership – were cited as the stumbling blocks to formal recognition by the GFSI of ISO 22000. It was thought that retailer-driven GFSI-benchmarked schemes had a "specific reactivity" and could implement changes agreed in the GFSI, whereas the

decision-making structures of the ISO were thought to be less conducive to “timely and efficient” adjustments in the light of changes in market conditions and demand.

2 EXISTING EUROPEAN AND INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

2.1 Identification of existing standards

Aquaculture and fisheries are ones of the most important sources of protein worldwide. Half of the seafood or the fish we eat comes from aquaculture; it is the fastest-growing food production system in the world.

However, as the industry expands, so does its footprint on the environment and on society. It is very important to anyone in the Aquatic industry to be able to face the challenge of minimizing these potentially negative impacts. One way to face this negative impact is to develop a robust and credible European and international standard for responsible aquaculture production.[5]

NOVAFOODIES project intends to help this wish by analyzing the already existing standards in the area and provide recommendation for improving already existing standards or for developing new standards or standardization documents.

Standards help reassure even customers that aquaculture products do not harm the environment or have social adverse impacts.

An industry that will expand by having self-regulation will be highly appreciated and welcomed especially in supplying valuable protein sources to ever increasing and rising populations, that have environmental respect on human values of responsibility. But this can only be done if we have a maintainable and sustainable practice that is adhered to throughout the Aquatic Industry.

In order to identify the relevant European and International standards related to the NOVAFOODIES project scope from the first year of the project (M9), the Romanian Standards Body (ASRO) performed a thoroughly research activity using the following means:

- The European and International Standardization Organizations platforms:
 - CEN <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>
 - CENELEC <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>
 - ISO <https://www.iso.org/home.html>
 - Official pages of other national standards organizations
- National Mirror Committees on healthy environmental-friendly and resilient farm to fork for identifying the potential homegrown standards relevant for NV.
- Input of partners according to knowledge and experience on pathogens and diseases, the number of “transmission channels” or “transport routes” for microorganisms to enter in a farm.

Following the research activity, 122 European, International and National standards of other countries were identified, both published documents and standardization projects. Out of those, 59 (41%) were ISO documents and 63 (39%) were CEN documents. Also, there were 29 (19%)

documents identified from the People's Republic of China and 2(1%) from New Zealand. (Annex A to this document)

This distribution can be observed in the following figure:

Figure 1. The general distribution of the identified standards

For the European standards the most relevant Technical Committees are:

- CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products
- CEN/TC 275 Food analysis – Horizontal methods
- CEN/TC 327 Animal feeding stuffs – Methods of sampling and analysis
- CEN WS ClimeFish

At International level the following Technical Committees and Organizations were identified:

ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture

ISO/TC 34 Food products

ISO/TC 207 Environmental management

ISO/TC 238 Solid biofuels

ISO/TC 308 Chain of custody

ISO/TMBG Technical Management Board - groups

ISO/TC 6 Paper, board and pulps

ISO/TC 69, Applications of statistical methods

ISO/TC 147 Water quality

ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information technology

ISO/TC 212 Medical laboratories and in vitro diagnostic systems

2.2 Presentation of the TCs

Amongst the most relevant, CEN/TC 454 “*Algae and algae products*”, deals with specification, classification, terminology, and determination methods for algae and algae-based products immediately derived from or used in algae production processes. In addition, guidance on the specific application of algae products as feedstock or intermediates for energy and non-energy products may be developed. Where specific standards for properties (quality or determination) of such feedstock for a certain industry exist, these will be referenced and considered as beyond the scope of the committee.

For the purpose of this committee algae and algae-based products (and their intermediates) are defined as algal biomass, algae extracts or purified compounds from algae, including photoautotrophic, autotrophic, mixotrophic and heterotrophic algae, harvested in the wild, or produced in open cultivation systems, as for example raceway ponds, lagoons and natural environment, and produced in closed systems, as for example photobioreactors, fermenters and other systems. For the purpose of this committee also Cyanobacteria are included, and Labyrinthulomycetes are also included because of the decision of the European Commission 2003/427/EC.

CEN/TC 275 – *Food analysis. Horizontal methods*, deals with standardization of methods of analysis for the detection and/or determination of - additives, residues, biotoxins and contaminants in food, - nutrients in food and food supplements, - irradiated foodstuffs, - food allergens and food substances causing intolerances, - genetically modified foodstuffs. In general, CEN/TC 275 does not elaborate standards on terminology, but sometimes on requirements/criteria for methods.

CEN/TC 327 *Animal feeding stuffs – Methods of sampling and analysis*, deals with standardization of methods of sampling and analysis for animal feeding stuffs, including chemical, biochemical, microbiological, physical and microscopical methods.

The international Technical Committees most relevant for the NOVAFOODIES project are:

ISO/TC 234 *Fisheries and aquaculture* is dealing with standardization in the field of fisheries and aquaculture, including, but not limited to, terminology, technical specifications for equipment and for their operation, characterization of aquaculture sites and maintenance of appropriate physical, chemical and biological conditions, environmental monitoring, data reporting, traceability and waste disposal.

ISO/TC 34 *Food products* is dealing with standardization in the field of human and animal foodstuffs, covering the food chain from primary production to consumption, as well as animal and vegetable propagation material, in particular, but not limited to, terminology, sampling, methods of test and analysis, product specifications, food and feed safety and quality management and requirements for packaging, storage and transportation.

ISO/TC 207 *Environmental management*, the very busy technical committee created in 1993, deals with standardization in the field of environmental management to address environmental and climate impacts, including related social and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development.

ISO/TC 238 *Solid biofuels*, deals with Standardization of terminology, specifications and classes, quality assurance, sampling and sample preparation and test methods in the field of raw and processed materials originating from arboriculture, agriculture, aquaculture, horticulture, and forestry to be used as a source for solid.

ISO/TC 308 *Chain of custody* is dealing with standardization in the field of Chain of Custody (CoC) for products and associated processes with specified characteristics, with the aim of ensuring that associated claims are reliable.

From the first list of identified standards, the partners selected the most relevant standards for the purpose of NOVAFOODIES project connected to their activities. Thus, the short list of most relevant standards was obtained, and this was the base of the entire activity (Annex B to this document).

The main domains of the selected standards are:

1. Algae and algae products
2. Management systems for food safety
3. Fisheries and aquaculture

The short list includes 33 European and International standards out of which 10 are CEN and 23 are ISO, as the figure 2 (left) below illustrates.

Published standards are 24, 7 are standardization documents and 2 are European/international standards under development, as figure 2 (right) illustrates.

Figure 2. *S standards selected for the analysis*

After this list of standards was decided upon, in order to ease the analysis of so many standards and to identify the gaps in standards or in the standardization work, ASRO developed a table of characteristics to be filled in by the interested partners.

3 STANDARDS ANALYSIS

3.1 Prerequisites

In order for the partners to be able to make the analysis of the selected standards, ASRO made the standards available on a SharePoint hosted by ASRO to be used only for the Project's purpose.

During the implementation of the Project, some other standards may be added to the list, upon request from the Partners.

Standards are copyright protected works, consequently, making them available meant for ASRO to take some precautions to ensure abiding by the legislation. Thus, each interested partner was asked to sign a Nondisclosure Agreement (NDA) (Annex C to this document) taking the responsibility of abiding by the copyright legislation on standards inside their company.

ASRO made sure that the SharePoint includes a folder with the list of selected standards, a folder with the texts of the standards, a folder with the list of interested Partners and a folder with the signed NDA's. Also, each standard was watermarked with "Not for distribution outside the NOVAFOODIES consortium" and was made available in a read only pdf. version.

For the analysis to be as easy and as friendly as possible, ASRO designed and developed a table to be filled in by the partners. This was also meant to make the gathering and the interpretation of the results more structured and comprehensive. The table was also made available in the SharePoint Table (Annex D to this document).

The list of selected standards and the table was also uploaded on the NOVAFOODIES project SharePoint.

3.2 The analysis

The following partners were interested in making the selection and analysis of the standards:

1. HOLOSS – Holistic and Ontological Solutions for Sustainability Ida.
2. IDENER
3. Lebensmittelversuchsanstalt LVA
4. Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research
5. CTAQUA – Centro Tecnológico de la Acuicultura
6. The National Center for Mariculture Israel Oceanographic&Limnological Research Ltd.
7. Gruppo Go Infoteam – Infoteam
8. Cyprus University of Technology

After conducting a comprehensive review of European and International standards related to more sustainable processes for providing the consumers with new functional, diversified, and traceable products of marine and freshwater origin, several gaps and uncovered needs have come to the attention of Consortium.

Environmental management

Among the numerous standards reviewed, those related to environmental management were first analysed, the EN ISO 14000 series.

ISO 14040:2006 *Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework* and ISO 14044:2006 *Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines* describes principles, framework, guidelines and requirements for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) phase, and

the assessment / interpretation phase. Furthermore, included the reporting and critical review of the life cycle assessment, limitations of the life cycle assessment, relationship between the life cycle assessment phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements.

They both cover LCA and LCI studies. However, do not have a description about the LCA technique in detail, nor do they specify methodologies for the individual phases of the life cycle assessment. The intended application of the results of LCA or LCI is considered during definition of the goal and scope, but the application itself is outside the scope of those International Standards. We have to pay attention that a LCA is a compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle (consecutive and interlinked stages of a product system, from raw material acquisition or generation from natural resources to final disposal).

The LCA addresses the environmental aspects and potential environmental impacts (e.g. use of resources and the environmental consequences of releases) throughout a product's life cycle from raw material acquisition through production, use, end-of-life treatment, recycling and final disposal. In a life cycle assessment study are four phases: the goal and scope definition phase, the inventory analysis phase, the impact assessment phase, and the interpretation phase. The scope, including the system boundary and level of detail, of a LCA depends on the subject and the intended use of the study. The depth and the breadth of LCA can differ considerably depending on the goal of a particular life cycle assessment. There are cases where the goal of a LCA can be satisfied by performing only an inventory analysis and an interpretation. This is usually referred to as a life cycle inventory study.

Being generic standards, the specific explanation on how to adopt the steps for different categories were not explained. Also, comparability becomes a problem because lack of explanation for each step. LCA typically does not address the economic or social aspects of a product, but the template of the standards can be used for economic and social assessments. Partners noticed that however, the possible ways to adapt the standards for novel technologies, like new functional products of marine and freshwater origin, has not been covered in the documents.

Water footprint

For water footprint, two documents were analysed, ISO 14046:2014 *Environmental management. Water footprint. Principles, requirements and guidelines* and ISO/TR 14073:2017 *Environmental management — Water footprint — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046*. International Standard ISO 14046:2014 provides principles, requirements and guidelines for conducting and reporting a water footprint assessment. Only air and soil emissions that impact water quality are included in the assessment, and not all air and soil emissions are included. The result of a water footprint assessment is a single value or a profile of impact indicator results. It does not go into details of choice of each parameter and the steps involved, providing a general idea for the assessment but not the clear picture. Whereas reporting is within the scope of ISO 14046:2014, communication of water footprint results, for example in the form of labels or declarations, is

outside the scope of ISO 14046:2014. For aquaculture, depending on either land based or offshore, the water management is essential to assess the environmental footprint. But the steps in the assessment are not elaborated.

On the other hand, technical report ISO/TR 14073:2017 provides illustrative examples of how to apply ISO 14046, in order to assess the water footprint of products, processes and organizations based on life cycle assessment. The examples are presented to demonstrate particular aspects of the application of ISO 14046 and therefore do not present all of the details of an entire water footprint study report as required by ISO 14046 and do not preclude alternative ways of calculating the water footprint, provided they are in accordance with ISO 14046. But, again, there are no examples specifically related to aquaculture or algal cultivation.

Examples are covering water footprint inventory of two power plants and of rice cultivation, water scarcity footprint of municipal water management, water scarcity footprint of rice cultivation (cradle-to-gate), water scarcity footprint of a textile with life cycle stages in different locations, water scarcity footprint of reservoir operation, reflecting seasonality, water scarcity footprint and water availability footprint of packaging production, water scarcity footprint differentiated by source of water, variation of water scarcity by forest management and land use, water eutrophication footprint of maize cultivation, calculated as one or two indicator results, comprehensive water footprint profile of packaging production, non-comprehensive weighted water footprint of cereal cultivation, water footprint of packaging production as part of a life cycle assessment, non-comprehensive water footprint of textile production, non-comprehensive weighted water footprint of municipal water management, non-comprehensive water footprint of a company producing chemicals (organization), water scarcity footprint of an aluminium company (organization), non-comprehensive direct water footprint of a hotel (organization) considering seasonality.

Climate adaptation

Another approach in searching valuable information was Climate Adaptation Plans for fisheries and aquaculture, and a CEN Workshop Agreement was examined, CWA 17518:2020 *Good practice recommendations for making Climate Adaptation Plans for fisheries and aquaculture*. This document provides recommendations for good practice for developing effective climate adaptation plans for production systems within the following sectors: marine wild capture fisheries, marine aquaculture, and lake and pond fisheries and aquaculture. In Europe, the algae sector is mostly dependant on wild harvesting. Making adaptation based on climate change from the results of the LCA is crucial to have a sustainable aquaculture system. The algae cultivation processes in NOVAFOODIES involve natural water sources widely influenced by climate change. Hence specific instructions on the application of the requirements in the case of algal cultivation or aquaculture is necessary. However, algae are not included in the list of sectors. This CWA can serve as a comparison to developed methods and as guidance to implement all current demands considering sustainability. It can be very useful as guidance for the sustainability approach.

Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies

Other partners had focused on documents related to blockchain and distributed ledger technologies, i.e. ISO/TR 16340:2023 *Application of blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food*, ISO 22739:2024 *Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Vocabulary* and ISO/TS 23635:2022 *Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Guidelines for governance*. Even if the technical quality was considered between average and good, it seems that all three documents contain just generic specifications. ISO/TR 16340:2023 is a useful tool for implement a blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food, not very deep into seafood sector, but generally applicable. It gives a good direction for system architecture design. ISO 22739:2024 is a vocabulary standard, giving generic technical definition about blockchain/ distributed ledger technologies, and had suffered minimal revision from 2020 version. The Technical Specification ISO/TS 23635:2022 was considered having a low coverage of the domain but it contains good generic specifications to implement a distributed ledger technologies registry, including risk and regulatory contexts for the governance.

Food safety management systems

In the field of Food safety management systems, the ISO 22000 series was analysed. The main standard, ISO 22000:2018 *Food safety management systems — Requirements for any organization in the food chain*, is considered useful for every part of the food supply chain - including NOVAFOODIES production sites. Food safety is related to the presence of food safety hazards at the time of consumption (intake by the consumer). Food safety hazards can occur at any stage of the food chain. Therefore, adequate control throughout the food chain is essential. Food safety is ensured through the combined efforts of all the parties in the food chain. This document adopts a process approach when developing and implementing a Food safety management system and improving its effectiveness to enhance the production of safe products and services while meeting applicable requirements.

Understanding and managing interrelated processes as a system contributes to the organization's effectiveness and efficiency in achieving its intended results. The process approach involves the systematic definition and management of processes, and their interactions, so as to achieve the intended results in accordance with the food safety policy and strategic direction of the organization. Management of the processes and the system as a whole can be achieved using the PDCA (Plan, Do, Check and Act) cycle, with an overall focus on risk-based thinking aimed at taking advantage of opportunities and preventing undesirable results. Another approach essential for achieving an effective food safety management system is risk-based thinking. In this document, risk-based thinking is addressed on two levels, organizational and operational. Risk is the effect of uncertainty, and any such uncertainty can have positive or negative effects. In the context of organizational risk management, a positive deviation arising from a risk can provide an opportunity, but not all positive effects of risk result in opportunities. The recognition of the organization's role and position within the food chain is essential to ensure effective interactive communication throughout the food chain.

The greatest problem when implementing a Food Safety Management System, FSMS, is to make sure the management and the employees know why and how a company needs a management system. In that context it would be helpful a section about how to explain the importance of a management systems and rules involved to employees and how to motivate them.

Technical Specifications ISO/TS 22002 (all parts) *Prerequisite programmes on food safety* were next examined in details. First Part, *Food manufacturing*, is a general guide on construction of buildings, handling and movement of workers and products to assure food safety, but no specification on fish or algae is made. It contains general requirements for food producing facilities (construction of buildings for food processing plants and connected processes (water supply, waste disposal, ventilation, etc.) with a focus on food safety. Sustainability /circular economy aspects are not discussed. Food manufacturing operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 apply to an individual establishment or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures implemented, these need to be justified and documented by a hazard analysis, as described in ISO 22000:2005.

Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of the organization to comply with the requirements. The second Part, *Catering*, makes no mention of specific food groups (for NOVAFOODIES would be fish or algae) and covers general food safety aspects regarding catering services. It would be useful, if NOVAFOODIES final products are offered in caterings - food handling and temperature chains are well described. The focus lies on food safety/consumer protection from foodborne pathogens and cross contaminations. Environmental topics are not covered. Next Part, *Part 3: Farming*, is about growing, harvesting and handling of aquatic animals, mentioning no aquacultures and no circular economy/ sustainability aspects. Even if third part deals with farming, aquatic farming is only described superficially, and in no relation with circular economy/sustainability aspects. ISO/TS 22002-4:2013, *Food packaging manufacturing*, is relevant for the project in terms of new packaging solutions like land-based seaweed culture for packaging, but not deals with e.g. waste optimisation or recycling of waste. The use of reusables (e.g. glass bottles) is not mentioned in the document (e.g. how they have to be cleaned), but recycled or plant-based materials are mentioned in the specification. This Technical Specification is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexities, that manufacture food packaging and/or intermediate products. *Part 5, Transport and storage*, matches in terms of transportation and storage of the end products and *Part 6, Feed and animal food production*, when producing feed of aquatic sources. ISO/TS 22002-5:2019 includes all food and feed products and food packaging and packaging materials, but is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain than in transportation and storage, or in isolation. Live animals are excluded from the scope of this document except when intended for direct consumption, e.g. molluscs, crustaceans and live fish. Feed and animal food operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in ISO/TS 22002-6:2016 necessarily apply to an individual organization or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures are implemented, these need to be justified by a hazard assessment and verified to be effective. Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of an organization to comply with other requirements contained in this Technical

Specification. The identified gap is considered the fact that there is no information about feed that is produced from residual material in a production site for food e.g. fish meal or if wastes/by-products from one level, become feed for another (like in systems as IMTA, Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture).

The last document studied on this approach is the one for traceability in the feed and food chain, ISO 22005:2007 *Traceability in the feed and food chain — General principles and basic requirements for system design and implementation*. This International Standard gives the principles and specifies the basic requirements for the design and implementation of a feed and food traceability system. It can be applied by an organization operating at any step in the feed and food chain. It is intended to be flexible enough to allow feed organizations and food organizations to achieve identified objectives. The traceability system is a technical tool to assist an organization to conform with its defined objectives, and is applicable when necessary to determine the history or location of a product or its relevant components. Indeed, a functioning traceability system is very important for a food and feed supply chain, to find the source of any possible problems or hazards very quickly. This includes fisheries and aquacultures, as well. But the information in the standard is very superficial, implementing a functioning traceability system will take a lot of time and resources.

Algae and algae products

The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) was requested by the European Commission (EC) to draft European standards or European standardization deliverables to support the implementation of Article 3 of Directive 2009/28/EC for algae and algae products. This request, presented as Mandate M/5471, also contributes to the Communication on “Innovating for Sustainable Growth: A Bio economy for Europe”. The former working group CEN Technical Board Working Group 218 “Algae”, was created in 2016 to develop a work programme as part of this Mandate. The technical committee CEN/TC 454 “Algae and algae products” was established to carry out the work programme that will prepare a series of standards.

The interest in algae and algae products has increased significantly in Europe as a valuable source including but not limited to carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, and several pigments. These materials are suitable for use in a wide range of applications from food and feed purposes to other sectors, such as textile, cosmetics, biopolymers, biofuel and fertilizer/biostimulants. Standardization was identified as having an important role in order to promote the use of algae and algae products. The work of CEN/TC 454 should improve the reliability of the supply chain, thereby improving the confidence of industry and consumers in algae and algae products and will promote and support commercialisation of the European algae industry.

As sector specific documents, for algae, from the ones developed by Technical Committee CEN/TC 454 *Algae and algae products*, the first standards examined were EN 17480:2021 *Algae and algae products - Methods for the determination of productivity of algae growth sites*, EN 17605:2022 *Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Sample treatment* and EN 17399:2020

Algae and algae products - Terms and definitions. Those standards are referring to methods to be used for the determination of the productivity of algae growth sites and the sample preparation of dry and wet samples of algae and algae products. These documents exclude methods for harvesting and pre/post-processing. Excluded as well is “wild growth”, which is defined as algae growing in nature without human interference except when harvesting the algae.

EN 17605:2022 specifies the sample preparation of dry and wet samples of algae and algae products and enables laboratories analysing algae samples to report accurate dry weight percentages and to obtain representative samples possible for further examination. Proper sample preparation is one of the crucial steps in obtaining the best possible result that most likely corresponds to the “true value”. All sample treatment steps depend on the different properties of the sample material and on the parameters to be analysed. Algae and algae products are biological materials, and not all parameters are stable. Therefore, special instructions concerning sample preparation for the different analysis methods are described. However, it is necessary to follow statutory regulations and, in every case, the sample size shall be large enough to be representative.

EN 17399:2020 is again a vocabulary standard, but its topic is too general: often not focused on algae-related terms. It has many concepts from biotechnology, but not pointing algae directly.

Another document issued by CEN/TC 454 and analysed by partners was technical report CEN/TR 17559:2022 *Algae and algae products - Food and feed applications: General overview of limits, procedures and analytical methods*, containing a general overview of available limits, procedures and analytical methods applicable to algae and algae products used for food and feed applications. This document does not apply to pharmaceutical, cosmetics, fertilizer/biostimulants, chemical and biofuel applications. It can be very useful, as it also outlines the use of algae as a novel food. Its limitations are: does not acquire a deep discussion of the topic (general ideas only) and is applicable to any field related to the use of algae (food technology, feed, biomass, etc.). Identified gaps were the slightly poor discussion about sustainability and the lack of methods of adaptation for consumption.

CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD

Seafood is generally recognized as a vital component of a balanced and nutritious diet due to its low-fat level and high protein content, as well as a variety of micronutrients such as vitamins and minerals. In addition, seafood is the principal dietary source of long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFAs or Omega-3), such as eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), which give a variety of health advantages, including a lower risk of cardiovascular disease. However, seafood is particularly perishable and degrades faster than other foods. Traditionally, a range of preservative approaches (such as curing, drying, fermentation, smoking, and conventional storage procedures; refrigeration and freezing) has been commonly applied to fish and other seafood, but they are not without limitations. Some of the challenges associated with the aforementioned traditional techniques include limited preservative usefulness, negative impact of sensory properties, high energy consumption, and hence, harmful effect on the environment. Many advanced technologies, such as ultrasound, irradiation, high-pressure processing, cold plasma,

radiofrequency, pulsed electric field, pulsed light technology, microwave processing, and packaging technologies (e.g., modified atmosphere, active, and intelligent packaging) have emerged in recent years with the advent of the 4IR (Fourth Industrial Revolution) technologies and have the potential to address the above referred challenges and to increase the shelf life of fish and other seafood during processing/and or preservation.

Safety, authenticity, traceability, nutritional quality, availability, convenience and integrity, and freshness are all important aspects of seafood quality. Conventional measurement methods of these quality aspects have been widely reported in the literature to determine sensory, physical, chemical, and microbial quality attributes. Traditional measurement methods (such as Kjeldahl method, colorimeter, texture analyzer, plate colony counting, etc.) have been extensively used to determine specific target attributes (such as chemical composition, color, texture, general appearance, biogenic amines, lipid and protein oxidation products, total volatile basic nitrogen, and microbial growth, among others). However, such analytical approaches are unlikely to be suitable for food Industry 4.0 due to their well-known limitations (e.g., time-consuming, destructive, etc.). Therefore, a variety of advanced techniques has been developed in recent years, including among others, various kinds of spectrometry, spectroscopic smart sensors, and hyperspectral imaging techniques. [5].

Standards are striving to keep up with the state of the art and represent the expression of the standard users to make new products and services accessible for every interested party.

The 33 selected standards were selected by 8 partners and the accent was put on:

- 9 CEN standards selected
- 1 CEN project selected
- 18 ISO standards selected
- 5 ISO projects selected

Out of the 8 participants, only 6 participants analysed the standards, which are as follows:

1. HOLOSS – Holistic and Ontological Solutions for Sustainability Ida.
2. IDENER
3. Lebensmittelversuchsanstalt LVA
4. Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research
5. Gruppo Go Infoteam – Infoteam
6. Cyprus University of Technology

The actual analysis of the standards is presented in Annex E to this document.

Not in the same order, the following statistics show how many standards were selected by each partner and how many were analysed:

- the first participant selected 5 standards and analysed them all
- the second participant selected 3 standards and analysed them all
- the third participant selected 7 standards and analysed only 4 standards
- the fourth participant selected 3 standards and analysed only 2 standards
- the fifth participant selected 13 standards and analysed them all

- the sixth participant selected 3 standards and analysed them all

Figure 3 – Distribution of the standards analysed by partners

The diagram shows the 6 partners and the number of standard each of them analysed.

6 analyses were submitted and 23 of the 33 selected standards have been analysed.

Out of the 23 analysed standards, 10 standards were analysed by several participants (2 or 3):

- CEN/TR 17559:2022 (3)
- ISO/TS 22002-4:2013 (3)
- ISO/TR 16340:2023 (2)
- ISO 22739:2024 (2)
- ISO/TS 23635:2022 (2)
- EN 17480:2021 (2)
- EN 17605:2022 (2)
- CWA 17518:2020 (2)
- ISO 14046:2014 (2)
- ISO/TR 14073:2017 (2).

Partners identified 6 standards as being highly important for the field in question and 11 as medium importance and a total of 25 gaps were identified and this only means that the standardization road map will be much more complex, improved and comprehensive than the present.

Proving to be the most known and used standards in the field of the NOVAFOODIES products and services, **the environmental management standards** were the first to be selected and analyzed. As a conclusion, partners noticed that the possible ways to adapt the standards for novel technologies, like new functional products of marine and freshwater origin, has not been covered in the documents, so this should be a starting point for the standards of the future in this area.

Concerning the **water footprint standards**, only 2 were analysed. Partners observed the lack of examples specifically related to aquaculture or algal cultivation.

A CWA (also a standardization document) analyzed **for the climate adaptation plans** and the conclusion was that specific instructions on the application of the requirements in the case of algal cultivation or aquaculture is necessary. However, algae are not included in the list of sectors. The conclusion is that this CWA can serve as a comparison to developed methods and as guidance to implement all current demands considering sustainability. It can be very useful guidance for the sustainability approach.

Some **blockchain and distributed ledger technologies standards** were specifically asked for by the partners and analyzed. The conclusion was that even that they do not go very deep into the seafood sector, they do offer a generally applicable direction and contain good generic specifications for implementing a distributed ledger technologies registry, including risk and regulatory contexts for the governance.

Speaking about the well-known food **safety management systems**, the ISO 22000 series was analysed. The standards, are considered useful for every part of the food supply chain with the following gaps:

- for the food safety management systems, it would be helpful to have a section about how to explain the importance of management systems and rules involved to employees and how to motivate them. There is no link between food safety and circular economy /sustainability (one health approach - critical, ethical and sustainable thinking).
- concerning the ISO/TS 22002 First Part, *Food manufacturing* - no specification on fish or algae is made and sustainability /circular economy aspects are not discussed. The second Part, *Catering*, makes no mention of specific food groups (for NOVAFOODIES would be fish or algae) and covers general food safety aspects regarding catering services. Part, *Part 3: Farming*, is about growing, harvesting and handling of aquatic animals, mentioning no aquacultures and no circular economy/ sustainability aspects. ISO/TS 22002-4:2013, *Food packaging manufacturing*, is relevant for the project in terms of new packaging solutions like land-based seaweed culture for packaging, but deals not with e.g. waste optimisation or recycling of waste. *Part 5, Transport and storage*, matches in terms of transportation and storage of the end products and *Part 6, Feed and animal food production*, when producing feed of aquatic sources. ISO/TS 22002-5:2019 includes all food and feed products and food packaging and packaging materials, but is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain than in transportation and storage, or in isolation.
- for **algae and algae products** 3 standards were analyzed. These were considered by the partners as being very useful but, in some ways, too general, not focused on algae relative terms, or do not acquire a deep discussion of the topic (general ideas only). Additionally, is applicable to any field related to the use of algae (food technology, feed, biomass, etc.). Identified gaps were the slightly poor discussion about sustainability and the lack of methods of adaptation for consumption.

As an overall conclusion, we can say that there are still many aspects of this relatively new field of global concern - new functional products of marine and freshwater origin - for which no standardization documents have yet been published to specify rules, recommendations and/or requirements to be respected.

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[2] Mihaela PILA, Nicoleta STĂNCIUC, Silviu STANCIU, *FISHERIES AND AQUACULTURE IN ROMANIA. A GLOBAL OUTLOOK ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT*, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați, 2023

[3] Sally Washington, Lahsen Ababouch, *Private standards and related certification schemes are becoming significant features of international fish trade and marketing*, FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper No. 553, 2011

[4] *** <https://www.iso.org/committee/541071.html>

[5] Abdo Hassoun, and others, *Seafood processing, preservation and analytical techniques in the age of industry 4.0*, 2022

ANNEXES

Annex A

No.	Technical committee (TC)	Standard/Project Reference	Standard Title	Keywords	Abstract/Scope	Status of standard	Standard category	Field of interest	Remarks
1	CEN/WS ClimeFish ³	CWA 17518:2020	Good practice recommendations for making Climate Adaptation Plans for fisheries and aquaculture	Climate Adaptation Plans, fisheries, aquaculture	This document provides recommendations for good practice for developing effective climate adaptation plans (CAPs) for production systems within the following sectors: marine wild capture fisheries, marine aquaculture, and lake and pond fisheries and aquaculture. NOTE The guidelines are in line with existing literature and adaptation tools on creating adaptation strategies and plans (e.g. FAO, 2019; Barange et al., 2018; ISO 14090, 2019; Brugère & De Young, 2015; Stahlne, 2014; EF, 2013; EURL, Spain & Eifeljan, 2011; Gordon, 2010)	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture, Sustainable production	
2	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	CEN/TR 17559:2022	Algae and algae products - Food and feed applications: General overview of limits, procedures and analytical methods	algae products, analytical methods	This document describes product specifications, product characteristics and other relevant information for algae and algae products for food, nutraceutical and animal feed applications. This document is a general overview of available limits, procedures and analytical methods applicable to algae and algae products used for food and feed applications. This document does not apply to pharmaceutical, cosmetics, fertilizer/biostimulants, chemical and	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
3	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	CEN/TR 17611:2021	Algae and algae products - Specifications for cosmetic sector applications	Algae, cosmetic sector	This document gives an overview of recommendations on product specifications, and other relevant information, for algae and algae products for cosmetics industry. This document does not apply to food and feed applications. This document does not provide instructions on handling of technical requirements in existing legislations.	Published	Basic standard	Sustainable production	
4	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	CEN/TR 17612:2021	Algae and algae products - Specifications for pharmaceutical sector applications	Algae, pharmaceutical sector	This document gives an overview of recommendations on product specifications, and other relevant information, for algae and algae products for pharmaceutical applications. This document does not apply to food and feed applications. This document does not provide instructions on handling of technical requirements in existing	Published	Basic standard	Sustainable production	
5	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	CEN/TR 17739:2021	Algae and algae products - Specifications for chemicals and biofuels sector applications	Algae, biofuels	The purpose of this document is to provide an overview on how quality indicating parameters for algae and algae products and intermediates relevant for chemical and bioenergy applications can be handled and to identify the need for future standards development for chemicals, bioenergy and biofuels applications. This document does not provide instructions on handling of technical requirements in	Published	Basic standard	Sustainable production	
6	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17399:2020	Algae and algae products - Terms and definitions	algae products, Terms	This document defines the terms related to functions, products, and properties of algae and algae products. In order to better pack the methodologies, algae are regarded as a functional group of organisms consisting of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes.	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae	
7	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17477:2021	Algae and algae products - Identification of the biomass of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes - Detection and identification with morphological and/or molecular methods	biomass, microalgae, macroalgae	This document specifies a method for the detection and identification of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes by using morphological methods and/or molecular methods. The morphological methods in this document are applicable to harvested wet biomass and to harvested dried unground biomass from microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes that have been grown and/or harvested for further processing and/or use. The molecular methods in this document are applicable to harvested wet biomass and to harvested dried and/or ground biomass from microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes that have been grown and/or harvested for further processing and/or use. This document describes a toolbox, consisting of several identification methods that can be chosen according to the applicability and purpose of the identification: - morphological methods based on observation and referring to scientific literature on taxonomy; - macroscopic identification; - light microscopic identification; - molecular methods for sequencing and blasting of sequences: - 16S rDNA sequencing; - 18S rDNA sequencing; - rbcL DNA sequencing; - ITS sequencing; - COX1 gene sequencing; - tufA gene sequencing. This document does not deal with genetic purity of the biomass or quantification of the identified taxa. This document is not suitable for the analysis of highly	Published	Basic standard	Biomass	
8	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17480:2021	Algae and algae products - Methods for the determination of productivity of algae growth sites	algae products, algae growth sites, productivity	This document specifies the methods to be used for the determination of productivity of algae growth sites. This document excludes methods for sampling, harvesting and pre-/postprocessing. Excluded as well is "wild growth", which is defined as algae growing in nature without human interference except when harvesting the algae.	Published	Basic standard	Sustainable production	
9	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17605:2022	Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Sample treatment	algae products, Sample treatment	This document specifies the sample preparation of dry and wet samples of algae and algae products. This document enables laboratories analysing algae samples to report accurate dry weight percentages and to obtain representative samples possible for further	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae	
10	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17908:2023	Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Determination of total lipids content using the Ryckebosch-Foubert method	algae products, analysis, total lipids content	This document specifies a laboratory method for the determination of the total lipid content in micro- and macroalgae by the Ryckebosch-Foubert method.	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae	
11	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17399:2024	Algae and algae products - Vocabulary	Algae, vocabulary	This document defines the terms related to functions, products and properties of algae and algae products. In order to better pack the methodologies, algae are regarded as a functional group of organisms consisting of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes.	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae	
12	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	FprEN 17980	Algae and algae products - Sampling - Guidelines for the definition of sampling programs and sampling protocols	algae products, sampling	This document specifies a set of principles and rules that algae producers, algae products industries, laboratories or other entities that collect algae and algae products samples can follow for the definition of their own sampling programs and sampling protocols. In the context of this document, algae are a functional group that include microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes. As algae and their production processes are so diverse, this document does not define a specific sampling program and/or a specific sampling protocol. Instead, this document specifies the aspects that can be considered when defining its own sampling program and protocol. This document describes when, where and how to draw a representative sample. For guidance on sample preparation of dry and wet samples of micro- and macroalgae, and algae products, please refer to EN 17605. This document is to be used for the collection of samples for lot characterization for commercial or legal/regulatory purposes. However, this document can also be used for any type of	Under Approval	Draft	Algae and macroalgae	

13	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	FprEN 17983	Algae and algae products - Measurement for renewable algal raw material for energy and non-energy applications	renewable algal, energy	This document specifies the methods to be used for the measurement of energy content and main elements balances of algae from cultivation or from wild growth and algae products to provide biomass, intended for renewable algal raw material used as bioenergy and in bio-based products. This document does not apply to methods of algae and algae products sampling, harvesting and pre/postprocessing. This document does not apply to algae and algae	Under Approval	Draft	Sustainable production	
14	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	prEN 18034	Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Determination of chlorophyll a content	algae products, chlorophyll	This document specifies a laboratory method for the determination of chlorophyll a content in algae. The method was initially tested and evaluated on the microalgae species Nannochloropsis and a heat treated algal product tomato soup with Nannochloropsis supplement, and the macro algae species Ulva sp, Furcellaria lumbricalis, and Saccharina latissima. During an Interlaboratory Trial the method was tested on the microalgae species Nannochloropsis and the macro algae species Saccharina latissima. The microalgae species Nannochloropsis and Phaeodactylum and the macro algae species Ulva sp and Saccharina latissima were tested in a Round Robin test. This document is only validated for chlorophyll a, but it can be used for other chlorophylls as well. If possible, an attempt will be made to incorporate an alternative method than the HPLC method proposed into the standard (informative or normative), on the condition that research on the use of a cheaper method fits into the budget allocated for this topic. The more, it is imperative that this additional method should obtain comparable results and accuracy as the HPLC method.	Under Enquiry	Draft	Consumer protection	
15	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products		Algae and algae products – Nitrogen content measurement and protein content calculation for micro- and microalgae	Nitrogen content, micro- and microalgae		Under Drafting	Draft	Consumer protection	
16	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products		Algae and algae products - Determination of the carotenoid content in algae	carotenoid content, algae		Under Drafting	Draft	Consumer protection	
17	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products		Algae and algae products – Determination of the polysaccharide content of macroalgae biomass	polysaccharide content, macroalgae biomass		Under Drafting	Draft	Biomass	
18	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products		Algae and algae Products – Determination of the fatty acid composition	fatty acid, algae Products		Under Drafting	Draft	Consumer protection	
19	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products		Algae and algae products – Determination of inorganic arsenic in algae and algae products by anion-exchange (HPLC-ICP-MS)	inorganic arsenic, algae products		Under Drafting	Draft	Consumer protection	
20	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products		Algae and algae products – Determination of the amino acid profile of micro- and macroalgae	microalgae, macroalgae, amino acid		Under Drafting	Draft	Consumer protection	
21	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products		Algae and algae products - Determination of the phycocyanin content in Arthrospira (Spirulina)	algae products, phycocyanin, Spirulina		Under Drafting	Draft	Consumer protection	
22	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	CEN/TS 16233-1:2011	Foodstuffs - HPLC method for the determination of xanthophylls in fish flesh - Part 1: Determination of astaxanthin and canthaxanthin	xanthophylls, fish flesh	This Technical Specification specifies a method for the determination of canthaxanthin and astaxanthin in fish flesh by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The method can be applied at a range above 0.02 mg/kg. The method should not be applied to the determination of canthaxanthin in poultry tissues, egg yolks and shrimp tissues due to a possible interference of canthaxanthin with cryptoxanthin and xanthophyll esters sometimes present in these	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
23	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	CEN/TS 16233-2:2011	Foodstuffs - HPLC method for the determination of xanthophylls in fish flesh - Part 2: Identification of the enantiomer ratio of astaxanthin	xanthophylls, fish flesh	This Technical Specification describes a method for the determination of the astaxanthin enantiomer ratio in fish flesh by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
24	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	CEN/TS 16621:2014	Food analysis - Determination of benzo[a]pyrene, benzo[a]anthracene, chrysene and benzo[b]fluoranthene in foodstuffs by high performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection (HPLC-FD)	benzo[a]pyrene, benzo[a]anthracene, chrysene, benzo[b]fluoranthene, foodstuffs	This Technical Specification specifies a method for the determination of benzo[a]pyrene (BaP) plus benzo[a]anthracene (BaA), benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF) and chrysene (CHR) in several food matrices. The method is based on size exclusion chromatography (SEC) cleanup, followed by quantification with high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with programmable fluorescence detection. This method has been in-house validated via the analysis of spiked samples of edible olive oil, fresh mussels, smoked fish, smoked meat products, processed cereal-based foods for young children, infant formulae, chocolate and food supplements (soflavones) at levels ranging from 0,25 µg/kg to 1,00 µg/kg and from 4,95 µg/kg to 23,53 µg/kg, depending on the Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon (PAH) or the matrix. This method complies with the performance characteristics specified for BaP, BaA, BbF and CHR in current legislation [3]. The method has been shown to be applicable to a variety of additional matrices as meat products, fresh fish, paprika, roasted coffee, bread, herbs, breakfast cereals, beer, sunflower oil, olives and fried tomato, with a limit of quantification below 0,5 µg/kg. In addition, the method was tested in-house and shown to be applicable also for the quantification of the other 12 PAHs of the 15+1 EU priority PAHs set (benzo[c]fluorene (BcF), benzo[k]fluoranthene (BkF), benzo[a]fluoranthene (Baf), dibenz[a,h]anthracene (DhA), dibenzo[a,e]pyrene (DeP), benzo[ghi]perylene (BghiP), dibenzo[a,h]pyrene (DhP), dibenzo[a,i]pyrene (DaiP), dibenzo[a,j]pyrene (DajP), indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene (IcdP), 5-methylchrysene (5MeC)) in all matrices listed above and at similar level ranges, except for CPP, where a UV detection had	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
25	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 14176:2017	Foodstuffs - Determination of domoic acid in raw shellfish, raw finfish and cooked mussels by RP-HPLC using UV detection	domoic acid, raw shellfish, raw finfish, cooked mussels	This European Standard specifies methods for the quantitative determination of domoic acid in raw bivalve molluscs and finfish as well as in cooked mussels. The limit of detection is about 10 ng/ml to 80 ng/ml (0,05 mg/kg to 0,4 mg/kg), depending on the UV detector sensitivity. The limit of quantification for DA by these methods is at least 2,7 mg/kg. Method A has been validated for the determination of DA in different raw matrices such as mussels, clams, scallops and anchovies, spiked and/or naturally contaminated at levels ranging from 2,7 mg/kg to 85,1 mg/kg. Method B has been validated for the determination of DA at levels ranging from 5 mg/kg to 12,9 mg/kg in cooked blue mussels. For further information on validation data, see Clause 8 and Annex A. Laboratory experience has shown that this standard can also be applied to other shellfish species, however, no	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	

26	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 14526:2017	Foodstuffs - Determination of saxitoxin-group toxins in shellfish - HPLC method using pre-column derivatization with peroxide or periodate oxidation	saxitoxin-group toxins, shellfish	This European standard specifies a method [1] for the quantitative determination of saxitoxin (STX), decarbamoyl saxitoxin (dcSTX), neosaxitoxin (NEO), decarbamoyl neosaxitoxin (dcNEO), gonyautoxin 1 and 4 (GTx1,4; sum of isomers), gonyautoxin 2 and 3 (GTx2,3; sum of isomers), gonyautoxin 5 (GTx5 also called B1), gonyautoxin 6 (GTx6 also called B2), decarbamoyl gonyautoxin 2 and 3 (dcGTx2,3; sum of isomers), N-sulfocarbamoyl-gonyautoxin 1 and 2 (C1,2; sum of isomers) and (depending on the availability of certified reference materials (CRMs)) N-sulfocarbamoyl-gonyautoxin 3 and 4 (C3,4; sum of isomers) in (raw) mussels, oysters, scallops and clams. Laboratory experience has shown that it is also applicable in other shellfish [2], [3] and cooked shellfish products. The method described was validated in an interlaboratory study [4], [5] and was also verified in a EURL-performance test aiming the total toxicity of the samples [6]. Toxins which were not available in the first interlaboratory study [4], [5] as dcGTx2,3 and dcNEO were validated in two additional interlaboratory studies [7], [8]. The lowest validated levels [4], [5], [8], are given in µg toxin (free base) per kg shellfish tissue and also as µmol/kg shellfish tissue and are listed in Table 1. A quantitative determination of GTx6 (B2) was not included in the first interlaboratory study but several laboratories detected this toxin directly after solid phase extraction with ion-exchange (SPE-COOH) clean-up and reported a mass concentration of 30 µg/kg or higher in certain samples. For that reason, the present method is applicable to quantify GTx6 (B2) directly, depending on the availability of the	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
27	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 16204:2012	Foodstuffs - Determination of lipophilic algal toxins (okadaic acid group toxins, yessotoxins, azaspiracids, pectenotoxins) in shellfish and shellfish products by LC-MS/MS	lipophilic algal toxins, shellfish	This European Standard specifies a multi-reference method for the determination of lipophilic algal toxins (fat-soluble algal toxins produced by some dinoflagellates) in raw shellfish and shellfish products including cooked shellfish, by liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry LC-MS/MS [1], [2], [3]. This method has been validated in an inter-laboratory study consisting of three parts via the analysis of both naturally contaminated homogenates of blue mussel and spiked extracts of blue mussel, oyster and clam. For further information on the validation, see Annex A. Additional studies have investigated further matrices (see [4], [5]). The detection limit for toxins of the okadaic acid group, azaspiracids and pectenotoxins was determined to be 6 µg/kg shellfish meat and for yessotoxins 10 µg/kg shellfish meat. Quantitative determination of okadaic acid (OA), pectenotoxin 2 (PTX-2), azaspiracid-1 (AZA-1) and yessotoxin (YTX) can be carried out directly by means of standard substances available commercially. Assuming an equal response factor, okadaic acid is used for the indirect quantitative determination of the two dinophysistoxins dinophysistoxin-1 (DTX-1) and dinophysistoxin 2 (DTX-2); likewise azaspiracid 1 (AZA-1) is used for the indirect quantitative determination of azaspiracid-2 (AZA-2) and azaspiracid-3 (AZA-3), while YTX is used for homo-yessotoxin, 4S-OH-yessotoxin and 4S-OH-homo-yessotoxin, and PTX-2 for pectenotoxin-1 (PTX-1). The limit of quantification (LOQ) for toxins of the okadaic acid	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
28	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 14332:2004	Foodstuffs - Determination of trace elements - Determination of arsenic in seafood by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GFAAS) after microwave digestion	arsenic, seafood	This document specifies a method for the determination of arsenic in seafood by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GFAAS) after microwave digestion [1], [2]. The collaborative study has included food having an arsenic content * 2 mg/kg dry matter. Specific foodstuffs for which European Standards exist are excluded from the scope of this horizontal document. It is the task of the analyst to	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
29	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 15517:2008	Foodstuffs - Determination of trace elements - Determination of inorganic arsenic in seaweed by hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry (HGAAAS) after acid extraction	trace elements, seaweed	This document specifies a procedure for the determination of hydrochloric acid (gastric acid concentration) extractable inorganic arsenic in seaweed. Collaborative studies have been carried out (Annex A). The method is suitable for the determination of inorganic arsenic not less than 1 mg/kg and below 100 mg/kg on a dry weight basis. The amount of inorganic arsenic is considered to be that part	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
30	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 17266:2019	Foodstuffs - Determination of elements and their chemical species - Determination of organomercury in seafood by elemental mercury analysis	organomercury, seafood	This document describes a method for the determination of organomercury in seafood/fishery products by elemental mercury analysis. The method has been successfully validated in an interlaboratory study with a working range from 0,013 mg/kg to 5,12 mg/kg (HORRAT values <2) in seafood/fishery products [1], [2]. The limit of quantification is approximately 0,010 mg/kg organomercury (referring to dry weight, expressed as mercury) [3], [4]. Organic species of mercury, other than monomethylmercury, are also extracted and thus determined with this method. However, in seafood/fishery products the contribution from organic species of	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
31	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 16801:2016	Foodstuffs - Determination of elements and their chemical species - Determination of methylmercury in foodstuffs of marine origin by isotope dilution GC-ICP-MS	methylmercury, foodstuffs, marine	This final draft European Standard describes a method for the determination of monomethylmercury (MMHg) in foodstuffs of marine origin. The method has been validated in an interlaboratory test on mussel tissue, squid muscle, crab claw muscle, dog fish liver, whale meat, cod muscle and Greenland halibut muscle (all freeze-dried) at levels from 0,04 mg/kg to 3,6 mg/kg dry weight according to ISO 5725 2 [1]. Laboratory experiences have shown that this method is applicable to fresh samples too.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
32	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 16802:2016	Foodstuffs - Determination of elements and their chemical species - Determination of inorganic arsenic in foodstuffs of marine and plant origin by anion-exchange HPLC-ICP-MS	inorganic arsenic, foodstuffs, marine	This draft European Standard describes a procedure for the determination of inorganic arsenic in foodstuffs of marine and plant origin by anion-exchange HPLC-ICP-MS following waterbath extraction. This method has been validated in an interlaboratory test on white rice, wholemeal rice, leek, blue mussels, fish muscle and seaweed with an inorganic arsenic mass fraction in the range 0,073 mg/kg to 10,2 mg/kg [1].	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
33	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	CEN/TS 15568	Foodstuffs - Methods of analysis for the detection of genetically modified organisms and derived products - Sampling strategies	Foodstuffs, sampling	This Technical Specification gives guidance for setting up valid sampling strategies for food products that are to be analysed for the presence of genetically modified organisms and derived products.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
34	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN ISO 22174:2005	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens - General requirements and definitions (ISO 22174:2005)	food-borne pathogens	ISO 22174:2004 gives the general requirements for the in vitro amplification of nucleic acid sequences (DNA or RNA). It is applicable to the testing of foodstuffs and isolates obtained from foodstuffs for food-borne pathogens using the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) The minimum requirements laid down in ISO 22174:2004 are intended to ensure that comparable and reproducible results are obtained in different laboratories. ISO 22174:2004 has been established for food-borne pathogens in or isolated from food and feed matrices, but is also applicable to other matrices (e.g. environmental samples) and for the detection of non-	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
35	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN ISO 4833-1:2013	Microbiology of the food chain. Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms. Part 1: Colony count at 30 degrees C by the pour plate technique (ISO 4833-1:2013)	food chain, colony count	This part of ISO 4833 specifies a horizontal method for enumeration of microorganisms that are able to grow and form colonies in a solid medium after aerobic incubation at 30 °C. The method is applicable to: a) products intended for human consumption and for animal feed; b) environmental samples in the area of food and feed production and handling. This part of ISO 4833 is applicable to: 1) products that require a reliable count when a low limit of detection is specified (below 102/g or 102/ml for liquid samples or below 103/g for solid samples); 2) products expected to contain spreading colonies that obscure colonies of other organisms, e.g. milk and milk products likely to contain spreading Bacillus spp. The applicability of this part of ISO 4833 to the examination of certain fermented food and animal feeds is limited and other media or incubation conditions can be more appropriate. However, this method can be applied to such products even though it is possible that the predominant microorganisms in those products are not detected effectively. For some matrices, the method specified in this part of ISO 4833 can give different results to	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards

36	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN 17266:2019	Foodstuffs - Determination elements and their chemical species - Determination of organomercury in seafood by elemental mercury analysis	organomercury, seafood	This document describes a method for the determination of organomercury in seafood/fishery products by elemental mercury analysis. The method has been successfully validated in an interlaboratory study with a working range from 0,013 mg/kg to 5,12 mg/kg (HORRAT values <2) in seafood/fishery products [1], [2]. The limit of quantification is approximately 0,010 mg/kg organomercury (referring to dry weight, expressed as mercury) [3], [4]. Organic species of mercury, other than monomethylmercury, are also extracted and thus determined with this method. However, in	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
37	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	FrEN 17855	Foodstuffs - Minimum performance requirements for quantitative measurement of the food allergens milk, egg, peanut, hazelnut, almond, walnut, cashew, pecan nut, brazil nut, pistachio nut, macadamia nut, wheat, lupine, sesame, mustard, soy, celery, fish, molluscs and crustaceans	performance requirement, quantitative measurement, fish	This document specifies minimum performance requirements for methods that quantify the food allergens milk, egg, peanut, hazelnut, almond, brazil nut, macadamia nut, cashew, pistachio nut, walnut, pecan nut, lupine, sesame, mustard, soy, celery, fish, molluscs, crustaceans, and wheat in raw and processed foodstuffs. Within the scope of this document, minimum requirements for an LOQ (Limit of Quantification) will be derived from threshold data of allergic consumers. For quantitative antibody-based methods, a normative annex will describe what specific information the method developer needs to deliver and how performance characteristics shall be validated. Regarding PCR and LC-MS/MS, information on performance characteristics are in parts covered by EN 15634-1 and EN 17644. This document does not apply to fragmented or hydrolysed food allergens, such as casein hydrolysates or soy sauce. It also does not apply to methods that deliver qualitative results only. Methods that cover gluten-containing cereals (wheat, rye, and barley) with regard to	Under Approval	Draft	Consumer protection
38	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	prEN 14526 rev	Foodstuffs - Determination of saxitoxin-group toxins in shellfish - HPLC method using pre-column derivatization with peroxide or periodate oxidation	saxitoxin-group toxins, shellfish	This European standard specifies a method [1] for the quantitative determination of saxitoxin (STX), decarbamoyl saxitoxin (dcSTX), neosaxitoxin (NEO), decarbamoyl neosaxitoxin (dcNEO), gonyautoxin 1 and 4 (GTX1,4; sum of isomers), gonyautoxin 2 and 3 (GTX2,3; sum of isomers), gonyautoxin 5 (GTX5 also called B1), gonyautoxin 6 (GTX6 also called B2), decarbamoyl gonyautoxin 2 and 3 (dcGTX2,3; sum of isomers), N-sulfocarbamoyl-gonyautoxin 1 and 2 (C1,2; sum of isomers) and (depending on the availability of certified reference materials (CRMs)) N-sulfocarbamoyl-gonyautoxin 3 and 4 (C3,4; sum of isomers) in (raw) mussels, oysters, scallops and clams. Laboratory experience has shown that it is also applicable in other shellfish [2], [3] and cooked shellfish products. The method described was validated in an interlaboratory study [4], [5] and was also verified in a EUROL-performance test aiming the total toxicity of the samples [6]. Toxins which were not available in the first interlaboratory study [4], [5] as dcGTX2,3 and dcNEO were validated in two additional interlaboratory studies [7], [8]. The lowest validated levels [4], [5], [8], are given in µg toxin (free base) per kg shellfish tissue and also as µmol/kg shellfish tissue and are listed in Table 1. A quantitative determination of GTX6 (B2) was not included in the first interlaboratory study but several laboratories detected this toxin directly after solid phase extraction with ion-exchange (SPE-COOH) clean-up and reported a mass concentration of 30 µg/kg or higher in certain samples. For that reason, the present method is applicable to quantify GTX6 (B2) directly, depending on the availability of the	Under Drafting	Draft	Consumer protection
39	CEN/TC 460 Food Authenticity	EN/TS 17303:2019	Foodstuffs - DNA barcoding of fish and fish products using defined mitochondrial cytochrome b and cytochrome c oxidase I gene segments	mitochondrial cytochrome, fish products	This document describes a procedure for the identification of single fish and fish fillets to the level of genus or species. The identification of fish species is carried out by PCR amplification of either a segment of the mitochondrial cytochrome b gene (cytb) or the cytochrome c oxidase I gene (cox1, syn COI) or both, followed by sequencing of the PCR products and subsequent sequence comparison with entries in databases. The methodology allows the identification of a large number of commercially important fish species. The decision whether the cytb or cox1 gene segment or both are used for fish identification depends on the declared fish species, the applicability of the PCR method for the fish species and the availability of comparative sequences in the public databases. This method has been successfully validated on raw fish fillets, however, laboratory experience is available that it can also be applied to processed, e.g. cold smoked, hot smoked, salted, frozen, cooked, fried, deep-fried samples. This document is usually unsuitable for the analysis of highly processed foods, e.g. tins of fish, with highly degraded DNA where the fragment lengths are not sufficient for amplification of the targets. Furthermore, it is not applicable for complex fish products containing	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
40	CEN/TC 460 Food Authenticity	EN ISO 20813:2022	Molecular biomarker analysis - Methods of analysis for the detection and identification of animal species in foods and food products (nucleic acid-based methods) - General requirements and definitions	Molecular biomarker, fishes	This document specifies minimum requirements of performance characteristics for the detection of nucleic acid sequences (DNA) by molecular methods, such as the polymerase chain reaction (PCR), including different post-PCR detection methods, real-time PCR, single and/or multiple probe-based detection techniques as well as the combination of such methods. The document is applicable to the detection, identification and quantification of DNA from animal species of higher and lower taxonomic groups in foodstuffs, and the validation of applicable methods. It is applicable to mammals, birds, reptiles, amphibians, fishes, molluscs, crustaceans and insects. Typical examples for each are listed in Annex A.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
41	CEN/TC 460 Food Authenticity	prEN ISO 17174	Molecular biomarker analysis - DNA barcoding of fish and fish products using defined mitochondrial cytochrome b and cytochrome c oxidase I gene segments (ISO/DIS 17174:2023)	Molecular biomarker, raw fish fillets	This document describes a procedure for the identification of single fish and fish fillets to the level of genus or species. The identification of fish species is carried out by PCR amplification of either a segment of the mitochondrial cytochrome b gene (cytb) [1] or the cytochrome c oxidase I gene (cox1, syn COI) [2], [3] or both, followed by sequencing of the PCR products and subsequent sequence comparison with entries in databases [4], [5]. The methodology allows the identification of a large number of commercially important fish species. The decision whether the cytb or cox1 gene segment or both are used for fish identification depends on the declared fish species, the applicability of the PCR method for the fish species and the availability of comparative sequences in the public databases. This method has been successfully validated on raw fish fillets, however, laboratory experience is available that it can also be applied to processed, e.g. cold smoked, hot smoked, salted, frozen, cooked, fried, deep fried samples. This document is usually unsuitable for the analysis of highly processed foods, e.g. tins of fish, with highly degraded DNA where the fragment lengths are not sufficient for	Under Enquiry	Draft	Consumer protection
42	CEN/TC 460 Food Authenticity	prEN 17881	Food authenticity - DNA barcoding of bivalves and products derived from bivalves using a defined mitochondrial 16S rRNA gene segment	bivalves	This document specifies a method for the taxonomic identification of a single bivalve or piece of bivalve to the genus or species level using DNA barcoding. It allows the identification of a large number of commercially important bivalve species. This method was validated on raw mussels. Laboratory experience indicates additional applicability to processed bivalve products, e.g. cold smoked, hot smoked, salted, frozen, cooked, fried, and deep-fried samples. The described method is usually unsuitable for the analysis of highly processed foods, e.g. tins of mussels, with highly degraded DNA where the fragment lengths are not sufficient for amplification of the target. Furthermore, it is not applicable for complex seafood products containing mixtures of two or more bivalve species. The identification of bivalve species is carried out by PCR amplification of a segment of the mitochondrial 16S rRNA gene, followed by sequencing of the PCR products and subsequent sequence comparison with entries in	Under Approval	Draft	Consumer protection

43	CEN/TC 230 Water analysis	EN 17211:2019	Water quality - Guidance on mapping of seagrasses and macroalgae in the eulittoral zone	mapping, macroalgae	This document provides guidance for survey design, equipment specification, survey methods, sampling and data handling of macroalgae and marine angiosperms such as <i>Zostera</i> in the intertidal soft bottom environment. It does not include polyurethylene terrestrial angiosperms that are found in saltmarshes. <i>Ruppia</i> is a genus of angiosperms that can be found in brackish water. This document can also be applied to the study of <i>Ruppia</i> in these environments. The document comprises: - development of a mapping and sampling programme; - requirements for mapping and sampling equipment; - procedures for remote sensing data collection; - procedures for direct mapping and sampling in the field; -	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae	
44	CEN/TC 230 Water analysis	EN ISO 10253:2016	Water quality - Marine algal growth inhibition test with <i>Skeletonema</i> sp. and <i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	Marine algal growth inhibition	ISO 10253:2016 specifies a method for the determination of the inhibition of growth of the unicellular marine algae <i>Skeletonema</i> sp. and <i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i> by substances and mixtures contained in sea water or by environmental water samples (effluents, elutriates, etc.). The method can be used for testing substances that are readily soluble in water and are not significantly degraded or	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
45	CEN/TC 230 Water analysis	EN ISO 8692:2012	Water quality - Fresh water algal growth inhibition test with unicellular green algae	green algae, algal growth inhibition	ISO 8692:2012 specifies a method for the determination of the growth inhibition of unicellular green algae by substances and mixtures contained in water or by waste water. This method is applicable for substances that are easily soluble in water. With modifications to this method, as specified in ISO 14442 and ISO 5667-16, the inhibitory effects of poorly soluble organic and inorganic materials, volatile compounds, heavy metals and waste water can be tested. A rapid algal growth inhibition screening test for waste water is described in an annex. An alternative test procedure with algae from algal beads, with	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae	
46	CEN/TC 230 Water analysis	EN 15204:2006	Water quality - Guidance standard on the enumeration of phytoplankton using inverted microscopy (Utermöhl technique)	quality, phytoplankton	The procedure described in this European Standard is based on the standard settling technique as defined by Utermöhl in 1958 [31]. It describes a general procedure for the estimation of abundance and taxonomic composition of marine and freshwater phytoplankton by using inverted light microscopy and sedimentation chambers, including the preceding steps of preservation and storage. Emphasis is placed on optimizing the procedure for the preparation of the microscopic sample. Many of the general principles of the approach described may also be applied to other techniques of enumerating algae (or other entities) using a (conventional) microscope, some of which are described in Annex E. This guidance standard does not cover field collection of samples or the analysis of picoplankton, quantitative analysis of free-floating mats of cyanobacteria or specific	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
47	CEN/TC 230 Water analysis	prEN ISO 10253	Water quality - Marine algal growth inhibition test with <i>Skeletonema</i> sp. and <i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	Marine algal growth inhibition	ISO 10253:2016 specifies a method for the determination of the inhibition of growth of the unicellular marine algae <i>Skeletonema</i> sp. and <i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i> by substances and mixtures contained in sea water or by environmental water samples (effluents, elutriates, etc.). The method can be used for testing substances that are readily soluble in water and are not significantly degraded or	Under Approval	Draft	Microbiology	
48	CEN/TC 463 Microbiology of the food chain	EN ISO 19343:2017	Microbiology of the food chain - Detection and quantification of histamine in fish and fishery products - HPLC method (ISO 19343:2017)	histamine, fish	ISO 19343:2017 specifies a high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method to analyse histamine in fish and fishery products (fish sauces, fish matured by enzyme in brine, etc.) intended for human consumption.	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
49	CEN/TC 463 Microbiology of the food chain	EN ISO 23036-1:2021	Microbiology of the food chain - Methods for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae in fish and fishery products - Part 1: UV-press method (ISO 23036-1:2021)	Anisakidae L3 larvae, fish	This document specifies a method for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae commonly found in marine and anadromous fishes. The method is applicable to fresh fish and/or frozen fish, as well as lightly processed fish products, such as marinated, salted or cold smoked. This method is applicable to quantifying parasitic infections by estimating the number of parasites in the fish musculature. This method does not apply to determining the species or genotype of detected parasites. Final identification is made by morphological	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
50	CEN/TC 463 Microbiology of the food chain	EN ISO 23036-2:2021	Microbiology of the food chain - Methods for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae in fish and fishery products - Part 2: Artificial digestion method (ISO 23036-2:2021)	Anisakidae L3 larvae, fish	This document specifies a method for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae commonly found in marine and anadromous fishes. The method is applicable to fresh fish and/or frozen fish, as well as lightly processed fish products, such as marinated, salted or smoked. It is also suitable for visceral organs as a confirmatory method for a visual inspection scheme. The artificial digestion method [4][5][6] is applicable to quantifying parasitic infections by estimating the number of parasites in the fish musculature and, when applied to fresh fish or lightly processed fish products (never frozen before processing), determining the viability of Anisakidae L3, which can be present. This method does not apply to determining the species or genotype of detected parasites. Final identification is made by	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
51	CEN/TC 463 Microbiology of the food chain	EN ISO 6887-3:2017	Microbiology of the food chain - Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination - Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products (ISO 6887-3:2017)	microbiological examination	ISO 6887-3:2017 specifies rules for the preparation of fish and fishery product samples and their suspension for microbiological examination when the samples require a different preparation from the methods described in ISO 6887-1. ISO 6887-1 defines the general rules for the preparation of the initial suspension and dilutions for microbiological examination. ISO 6887-3:2017 includes special procedures for sampling raw molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms from primary production areas. NOTE 1 Sampling of raw molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms from primary production areas is included in this document, rather than ISO 13307, which specifies rules for sampling from the terrestrial primary production stage. ISO 6887-3:2017 excludes preparation of samples for both enumeration and detection test methods where preparation details are specified in the relevant International Standards (e.g. ISO/TS 15216-1 and ISO/TS 15216-2 for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus in food using real-time RT-PCR). ISO 6887-3:2017 is intended to be used in conjunction with ISO 6887-1. It is applicable to the following raw, processed or frozen fish and shellfish and their products (see Annex A for classification of major taxa): a) Raw fishery products, molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms including: - whole fish or fillets, with or without skin and heads, and gutted; - crustaceans, whole or shelled; - cephalopods; - bivalve molluscs; - gastropods; - tunicates and echinoderms. b) Processed products including: - smoked fish, whole or prepared fillets, with or without skin; - cooked or partially cooked, whole or shelled crustaceans, molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms; - cooked or partially cooked fish and fish-based multi-component products. c) Raw or cooked frozen fish, crustaceans, molluscs and others, in blocks or otherwise,	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
52	CEN/TC 463 Microbiology of the food chain	EN ISO 6887-3:2017/A1:2020	Microbiology of the food chain - Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination - Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products - Amendment 1: Sample preparation for raw marine gastropods (ISO 6887-3:2017/Amd 1:2020)	microbiological examination	Microbiology of the food chain - Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination - Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products - Amendment 1: Sample preparation for raw marine gastropods (ISO 6887-3:2017/Amd 1:2020)	Published	Amendment	Microbiology	
53	CEN/TC 308 Characterization of sludges	EN 12880:2000	Characterization of sludges - Determination of dry residue and water content	sludges, dry residue	This European Standard specifies a method for the determination of dry residue and water content of sludges and sludge products. This method is applicable to the determination of dry residue and water content of sludges which include liquid, paste-like or solid matter.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards

54	CEN/TC 19 - Petroleum products, lubricants and related products	EN 15293:2018	Automotive fuels - Automotive ethanol (E85) fuel - Requirements and test methods	ethanol fuel	This document specifies requirements and test methods for marketed and delivered automotive ethanol (E85) fuel. It is applicable to automotive ethanol (E85) fuel for use in spark ignition engine vehicles designed to run on automotive ethanol (E85) fuel. Automotive ethanol (E85) fuel is a mixture of nominally 85 % (V/V) ethanol and unleaded petrol, but also including the possibility of having different "seasonal grades" containing more than 50 % (V/V) ethanol. NOTE 1 For the purposes of this document, the terms "% (m/m)" and "% (V/V)" are used to represent respectively the mass fraction and the volume fraction.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
55	CEN/TC 19 - Petroleum products, lubricants and related products	CEN/TR 16389	Automotive fuels - Paraffinic diesel fuel and blends with FAME - Background to the parameters required and their respective limits and determination	limits, determination	This Technical Report explains the requirements and test methods for marketed and delivered paraffinic diesel as such from synthesis (XTL) or hydrotreatment (HVO) and of blends thereof with up to 7%(V/V) of fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) according to European fuel specifications. It provides background information to judge the final text of the European Standard EN 15940 and gives guidance and explanations to the producers, blenders, marketers and users of paraffinic automotive diesel. Paraffinic diesel is a high quality, clean burning fuel with virtually no sulfur and aromatics. Paraffinic diesel fuel can be used in diesel engines, also to reduce regulated emissions. In order to have the greatest possible emissions reduction, a specific calibration may be necessary. Paraffinic diesel fuel can also offer a meaningful contribution to the target of increased non-crude derived and/or renewable content in transportation fuel pool. For general diesel engine warranty, paraffinic automotive diesel fuel may need a validation step to confirm the compatibility of the fuel with the vehicle, which for some existing engines may still need to be done. The vehicle manufacturer needs to be consulted before use. NOTE 1 This document is directly related to the development of EN 15940 and will be updated once further publications take place. NOTE 2 Paraffinic diesel is also used as a blending component in	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
56	CEN/TC 19 - Petroleum products, lubricants and related products	EN 15376:2014	Automotive fuels - Ethanol as a blending component for petrol - Requirements and test methods	ethanol, petrol	This European Standard specifies requirements and test methods for marketed and delivered ethanol to be used as an extender for automotive fuel for petrol engine vehicles in accordance with the requirements of EN 228 [5]. It is applicable to ethanol used for blending at all levels up to and including 85 % (V/V). NOTE For the purposes of this document, the term "% (m/m)" and "% (V/V)" are used to represent the mass fraction, μ , and the volume fraction, ϕ , respectively.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
57	CEN/TC 408 - Project Committee - Biomethane for use in transport and injection in natural gas pipelines	EN 16723-2:2017	Natural gas and biomethane for use in transport and biomethane for injection in the natural gas network - Part 2: Automotive fuels specification	biomethane, transport	This European Standard specifies the requirements and test methods for natural gas (group L and H, as in EN 437), biomethane and blends of both at the point of use as automotive fuels. This European Standard applies to the previously mentioned fuels irrespective of the storage state (compressed or liquefied). To check compliance with some requirements set by the standard, LNG or liquefied biomethane should be re-gasified prior to testing.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
58	CEN/TC 345 Characterization of soils	EN ISO 11074:2015	Soil quality - Vocabulary	soil, quality	This International Standard defines a list of terms used in the preparation of the standards in the field of soil quality. The terms are classified under the following main headings: — general terms (terms relating to soil, soil materials, land, and sites); — description of soil (soil characteristics, soil water, properties of soils and substances, processes in soil, contamination, pollution, background content); — sampling (general terms, sample types/sampling type, sampling stages, execution of sampling, quality control samples, sample pretreatment); — terms relating to the assessment of soils (quality, assessment of soil and sites with respect to risk, hazard and exposure, soil protection); — remediation (general terms, principal remediation types, engineering-based methods, process-based treatment methods).	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
59	CEN/TC 335 - Solid biofuels	EN ISO 18122:2022	Solid biofuels - Determination of ash content	biofuels, ash	This document specifies a method for the determination of ash content of all solid biofuels.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
60	CEN/TC 307 Oilseeds, vegetable and animal fats and oils and their by-products - Methods of sampling and analysis	EN ISO 3596:2001	Animal and vegetable fats and oils - Determination of unsaponifiable matter - Method using diethyl ether extraction	fats, unsaponifiable matter	This International Standard specifies a method using diethyl ether extraction for the determination of the unsaponifiable matter content of animal and vegetable fats and oils. This method is not applicable to waxes and, moreover, gives approximate results with certain fats of high unsaponifiable matter content, for example with fats derived from marine animals. A method given in ISO 18609 may be used when climatic conditions, or regulations, do not permit the use of diethyl ether.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
61	CEN/TC 307 Oilseeds, vegetable and animal fats and oils and their by-products - Methods of sampling and analysis	EN ISO 659:2009	Oilseeds - Determination of oil content (Reference method)	oilseed, oil content	This International Standard specifies a reference method for the determination of the hexane extract (or light petroleum extract), called the "oil content", of oilseeds used as industrial raw materials. The procedure for sunflower seed is different from those for other seeds as it includes an additional moisture content determination after the seed has been ground to prepare the test sample. The method has been tested on rapeseed, soya beans and sunflower seed. This does not, however, preclude its applicability to other commercial seeds. If required, the pure seeds and the impurities (see 9.4) can be analysed separately. In the case of groundnuts (see 10.1.6), the pure seeds, the total fines, the non-oleaginous impurities and the	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
62	CEN/TC 307 Oilseeds, vegetable and animal fats and oils and their by-products - Methods of sampling and analysis	EN ISO 3961:2018	Animal and vegetable fats and oils - Determination of iodine value (ISO 3961:2018)	fats, iodine value	This document specifies a reference method for the determination of the iodine value (commonly known in the industry as IV) of animal and vegetable fats and oils, hereinafter referred to as fats. Annex B describes a method for the calculation of the IV from fatty acid compositional data. This method is not applicable to fish oils. Furthermore, cold-pressed, crude and unrefined vegetable oils as well as (partially) hydrogenated oils can give different results by the two methods. The calculated IV is affected by impurities and thermal	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
63	CEN/TC 327 Animal feeding stuffs - Methods of sampling and analysis	EN ISO 6498:2012	Animal feeding stuffs - Guidelines for sample preparation (ISO 6498:2012)	feeding stuffs, sample	This International Standard specifies guidelines for the preparation of test samples from laboratory samples of animal feeding stuffs, including pet foods. NOTE 1 The guidelines mostly derive from those developed by AAFCO (see Reference [7]). The guidelines are overruled by special instructions and regulations for sample preparation demanded by specific analysis methods. NOTE 2 Such analysis methods are developed by ISO and CEN. NOTE 3 This International Standard does not include special guidelines for sample preparation for microbiological analysis of microorganisms like yeasts, bacteria and moulds. Nonetheless, for microorganisms which are used as feed additives (probiotics), some important aspects	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards

No.	Technical committee (TC)	Sub committee (SC) / Working Group (WG)	Standard/Project Reference	Standard Title	Keywords	Abstract/Scope	Status of standard	Standard category	Field of interest	Remarks
1	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO 22000:2018	Food safety management systems — Requirements for any organization in the food chain	Food safety management systems, food chain	This document specifies requirements for a food safety management system (FSMS) to enable an organization that is directly or indirectly involved in the food chain: a) to plan, implement, operate, maintain and update a FSMS providing products and services that are safe, in accordance with their intended use; b) to demonstrate compliance with applicable statutory and regulatory food safety requirements; c) to evaluate and assess mutually agreed customer food safety requirements and to demonstrate conformity with them; d) to effectively communicate food safety issues to interested parties within the food chain; e) to ensure that the organization conforms to its stated food safety policy; f) to demonstrate conformity to relevant interested parties; g) to seek certification or registration of its FSMS by an external organization, or make a self-assessment or self-declaration of conformity to this document. All requirements of this document are generic and are intended to be applicable to all	Under development ISO/AWI 22000 ISO 22000:2018/Amd 1	Basic standard	Management systems for food certification	
2	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-1:2009	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 1: Food manufacturing	food safety, food manufacturing	ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRP) to assist in controlling food safety hazards. ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, which are involved in the manufacturing step of the food chain and wish to implement PRP in such a way as to address the requirements specified in ISO 22000:2005, Clause 7. ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain. Food manufacturing operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 apply to an individual establishment or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures implemented, these need to be justified and documented by a hazard analysis, as described in ISO 22000:2005, 7.4. Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of the organization to comply with these requirements. Examples of such exclusions include the additional aspects relevant to manufacturing operations listed under 1), 2), 3), 4), and 5) below.	Under development ISO/CD 22002-1	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
3	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-2:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 2: Catering	food safety, catering	ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 specifies the requirements for the design, implementation, and maintenance of prerequisite programmes (PRPs) to assist in controlling food safety hazards in catering. ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 is applicable to all organizations which are involved in the processing, preparation, distribution, transport, and serving of food and meals and wish to implement PRPs in accordance with the requirements specified in ISO 22000:2005, 7.2. The scope of ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 includes catering, air catering, railway catering, banquets, among others, in central and satellite units, school and industry dining rooms, hospitals and healthcare facilities, hotels, restaurants, coffee shops, food services, and food stores. Users of catering can belong to vulnerable groups, such as children, elderly and/or ill people. In some countries, the term "food services" is used synonymously with catering. The application of ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 does not exempt the user from compliance with current and applicable legislation. Where local legal requirements are in specified for parameters	Under development ISO/CD 22002-2	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
4	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-3:2011	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 3: Farming	food safety, farming	ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 specifies requirements and guidelines for the design, implementation, and documentation of prerequisite programmes (PRPs) that maintain a hygienic environment and assist in controlling food safety hazards in the food chain. ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 is applicable to all organizations (including individual farms or groups of farms), regardless of size or complexity, which are involved in farming steps of the food chain and wish to implement PRPs in accordance with ISO 22000:2005, 7.2. If an organization is using ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 as a reference for the purpose of making a self-declaration of conformity with or seeking certification to ISO 22000:2005, deviations therefrom (i.e. where exclusions are made or alternative measures are implemented) need to be justified and documented. It is expected that such deviations will not affect the ability of the organization to comply with the requirements of ISO 22000. ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 is applicable to the farming of crops (e.g. cereals, fruits, vegetables), living farm animals (e.g. cattle, poultry, pigs, fish) and the handling of their products (e.g. milk, eggs). It is not applicable to activities such as picking of wild fruits, vegetables and mushrooms, fishing,	under review	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
5	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-4:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 4: Food packaging manufacturing	food safety, food packaging manufacturing	ISO/TS 22002-4:2013 specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) to assist in controlling food safety hazards in the manufacture of food packaging. This Technical Specification is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexities that manufacture food packaging and/or intermediate products.	Under development ISO/CD 22002-4	Basic standard	Consumer protection	

6	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-5:2019	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 5: Transport and storage	food safety, transport and storage	This document specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) for transport and storage in the food chain to assist in controlling food safety hazards. This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, that are involved in transport and storage activities across the food supply chain and that wish to implement PRPs in such a way as to address the requirements specified in ISO 22000. This document is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain or in isolation. In this document, transport and storage is aligned with ISO/TS 22003:2013, Annex A, Category G. This document includes all food and feed products and food packaging and packaging materials. Live animals are excluded from the scope of this document except when intended for direct consumption, e.g. molluscs, crustaceans and live fish.	Under development ISO/CD 22002-5	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
7	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-6:2016	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 6: Feed and animal food production	food safety, feed and animal food production	ISO/TS 22002-6:2016 specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) to assist in controlling feed safety hazards in feed and animal food and in materials intended for use in the production of feed and animal food. Feed safety hazards in this context relate to attributes that have a potential to affect adversely animal and/or human health. Prerequisite programmes are intended to ensure feed safety and to prevent, control and detect potential contamination including cross-contamination that could occur under the responsibility of the organization. ISO/TS 22002-6:2016 is applicable to all organizations regardless of size, location or complexity that are involved in the manufacturing and/or supply of feed and animal food and wish to implement a PRP. Feed and animal food operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in this Technical Specification necessarily apply to an individual organization or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures are implemented, these need to be justified by a hazard assessment and verified to be effective. Any exclusions or alternative	Under development ISO/CD 22002-6	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
8	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO 22003-1:2022	Food safety — Part 1: Requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of food safety management systems	Food safety, audit, certification	This document specifies the requirements for the audit and certification of a food safety management system (FSMS) complying with the requirements given in ISO 22000 (or other specified FSMS requirements). It also provides the necessary information and confidence to customers about the way certification of their suppliers has been granted. Certification of FSMS is a third-party conformity assessment activity (as described in ISO/IEC 17000:2020, 4.3), and bodies performing this activity are third-party conformity assessment bodies. NOTE 1 In this document, the terms "product" and "service" are used separately (in contrast with the definition of "product" given in ISO/IEC 17000). NOTE 2 This document can be used as a criteria document for the accreditation or peer assessment of certification bodies which seek to be recognized as being competent to certify that an FSMS complies with ISO 22000 or other sets of specified FSMS requirements. It is also intended to be used as a criteria document by regulatory authorities and industry consortia which engage in direct recognition of certification bodies to certify that an FSMS	Published	Basic standard	Management systems for food certification	
9	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO 22003-1:2022	Food safety — Part 2: Requirements for bodies providing evaluation and certification of products, processes and services, including an audit of the food safety system	Food safety, audit, certification	This document is supplemental to ISO/IEC 17065. It specifies the rules applicable for the audit of a food safety system (FSS) and certification of products, processes and services complying with requirements of a certification scheme that is based on the internationally accepted principles of food safety (e.g. CODEX General Principles of Food Hygiene[8]) and includes management system elements. This document does not apply to certifications that are solely based on product testing (e.g. performed by an organization applying ISO/IEC 17025) or inspection (e.g. performed by an organization applying ISO/IEC 17020) and does not apply to ISO/IEC 17065-based food safety schemes that do not include both internationally accepted principles of food safety and management system elements. It also provides the necessary information and confidence to customers about the way certification of their suppliers has been granted. Certification of FSS is a third-party conformity assessment activity (as described in ISO/IEC 17000:2020, 4.3) and bodies performing this activity are third-party conformity assessment bodies. NOTE This document can be used as a criteria	Published	Basic standard	Management systems for food certification	
10	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO 22005:2007	Traceability in the feed and food chain — General principles and basic requirements for system design and implementation	Traceability, system design, implementation	ISO 22005:2007 gives the principles and specifies the basic requirements for the design and implementation of a feed and food traceability system. It can be applied by an organization operating at any step in the feed and food chain. It is intended to be flexible enough to allow feed organizations and food organizations to achieve identified objectives. The traceability system is a technical tool to assist an organization to conform with its defined objectives, and is applicable when necessary to determine the history or location of a product or its relevant components.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	

11	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/AWI 22002-7	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 7: Retail	food safety, retail	This document specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRP) to assist in controlling food safety hazards. This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, which are involved in the retail step of the food chain and wish to implement PRP in such a way as to address the requirements specified in ISO 22000:2018, Clause 8. This document is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain. Food retail operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in this document apply to an individual establishment or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures implemented, these need to be justified and documented by a hazard analysis, as described in ISO 22000:2018, 8.5.2. Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of the organization to comply with these requirements. Examples of such exclusions include the additional aspects relevant to manufacturing operations listed under 1), 2), 3), 4), and 5) below. This document specifies detailed requirements to be specifically considered in relation to ISO	Under development ISO/AWI 22002-7	Draft	Consumer protection	
12	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/CD 22002-100	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 100: PRP requirements common for food, feed, and packaging supply chain	food safety, packaging		Under development ISO/CD 22002-100	Draft	Consumer protection	
13	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 6 Meat, poultry, fish, eggs and their products	ISO 23855:2021	Frozen surimi	fish	This document specifies the requirements for frozen surimi and the test methods for its quality control. It also specifies the requirements of packaging, marking, storage and transportation. This document specifies the requirements for frozen surimi and the test methods for its quality control. It also specifies the requirements of packaging, marking, storage and transportation. This document is applicable to tropical and cold-water surimi. This document is applicable to tropical and cold-water surimi.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	
14	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 6 Meat, poultry, fish, eggs and their products	ISO/WD 17644	Determination of paralytic shellfish toxins in bivalve mollusks — HPLC-MS/MS	shellfish, toxins, mollusks	The proposal of this new work item is to develop detection standard of "Determination of paralytic shellfish toxins in bivalve mollusks by HPLC-MS/MS". The detection standard formulation mainly includes seven parts: (1) Scope; (2) Normative references; (3) Terms and definitions; (4) Principle; (5) Sampling; (6) Preparation of test sample; (7) Test method of liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry.	Under development ISO/WD 17644	Draft	Consumer protection	
15	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 6 Meat, poultry, fish, eggs and their products	ISO/CD 17648	Quick-frozen coated aquatic products Specification	aquatic products, frozen	The proposal of this new work item is to develop the standard of "Quick-frozen coated aquatic products". The standard specifies the requirements for quick-frozen coated aquatic products and the test methods for quality control. It also specifies the requirements of packaging, marking, storage and transportation. The standard is applicable to quick-frozen aquatic products-breaded or in batter made from finfish, crustaceans, molluscan shellfish and cephalopods through pre-treatment, wet and dry coating, and quick freezing, which are raw or pre-cooked products.	Under development ISO/CD 17648	Draft	Consumer protection	
16	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 6 Meat, poultry, fish, eggs and their products	ISO/WD 19615	Meat and fish products — Determination of volatile basic nitrogen — Semi-micro nitrogen determination method	fish products, nitrogen	This new work item proposal specifies a routine method for determination of volatile basic nitrogen in meat and fish products: semi-micro nitrogen determination method. In this method, the test sample is deproteinised by a solution of trichloroacetic acid. Then the extract is put into the apparatus for steam distillation. As volatile basic nitrogen is volatile, steam distillation makes volatile basic nitrogen of the extract easily produce in the process of alkalisation. The volatile nitrogenous base components are then absorbed by an acid receiver. Finally, the volatile basic nitrogen concentration is determined by acid-base titration of the absorbed bases. This proposed new work item proposal is applicable to the determination of volatile basic nitrogen in food with meat and fish as the main raw materials, including livestock, poultry, egg and fish products.	Under development ISO/WD 19615	Draft	Consumer protection	
17	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 6 Meat, poultry, fish, eggs and their products	ISO/AWI 23883	Meat, fish and their products — Determination of fluoroquinolones residues content — High performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry method	fluoroquinolones, fish	The proposed new work specifies the high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) method for the determination of fluoroquinolones residues content in meat, fish and their products. This document is applicable to the determination of fluoroquinolones residues in meat, fish and their products, including livestock and poultry.	Under development ISO/AWI 23883	Draft	Consumer protection	
18	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 6887-3:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products	test samples, microbiology, fish	ISO 6887-3:2017 specifies rules for the preparation of fish and fishery product samples and their suspension for microbiological examination when the samples require a different preparation from the methods described in ISO 6887-1. ISO 6887-1 defines the general rules for the preparation of the initial suspension and dilutions for microbiological examination. ISO 6887-3:2017 includes special procedures for sampling raw molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms from primary production areas. NOTE 1 Sampling of raw molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms from primary production areas is included in this document, rather than ISO 15307, which specifies rules for sampling from the terrestrial primary production stage. ISO 6887-3:2017 excludes preparation of samples for both enumeration and detection test methods where preparation details are specified in the relevant International Standards (e.g. ISO/TS 15216-1 and ISO/TS 15216-2 for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus in food using real-time RT-PCR). ISO 6887-3:2017 is intended to be used in conjunction with ISO 6887-1. It is applicable to the following raw, processed or frozen fish and	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
19	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 6887-3:2017/Amd 1:2020	Microbiology of the food chain Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products -	test samples, microbiology, fish		Published	Amendment	Microbiology	

20	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 19943:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Detection and quantification of histamine in fish and fishery products — HPLC method	Microbiology, histamine, fish	ISO 19943:2017 specifies a high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method to analyse histamine in fish and fishery products (fish sauces, fish matured by enzyme in brine, etc.) intended for human consumption.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Microbiology	
21	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 23036-1:2021	Microbiology of the food chain — Methods for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae in fish and fishery products — Part 1: UV-press method	Anisakidae L3 larvae, fish, UV	This document specifies a method for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae commonly found in marine and anadromous fishes. The method is applicable to fresh fish and/or frozen fish, as well as lightly processed fish products, such as marinated, salted or cold smoked. This method is applicable to quantifying parasitic infections by estimating the number of parasites in the fish musculature. This method does not apply to determining the species or genotype of detected parasites. Final identification is made by morphological and/or molecular methods.	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
22	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 23036-2:2021	Microbiology of the food chain — Methods for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae in fish and fishery products — Part 2: Artificial digestion method	Anisakidae L3 larvae, fish, digestion	This document specifies a method for the detection of Anisakidae L3 larvae commonly found in marine and anadromous fishes. The method is applicable to fresh fish and/or frozen fish, as well as lightly processed fish products, such as marinated, salted or smoked. It is also suitable for visceral organs as a confirmatory method for a visual inspection scheme. The artificial digestion method[4][5][6] is applicable to quantifying parasitic infections by estimating the number of parasites in the fish musculature and, when applied to fresh fish or lightly processed fish products (never frozen before processing), determining the viability of Anisakidae L3, which can be present. This method does not apply to determining the species or genotype of detected parasites. Final identification is made by morphological and/or molecular methods.	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	
23	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 12875:2011	Traceability of finfish products — Specification on the information to be recorded in captured finfish distribution chains	captured finfish, distribution chains	ISO 12875:2011 specifies the information to be recorded in marine-captured finfish supply chains in order to establish the traceability of products originating from captured finfish. It specifies how traded fishery products are to be identified, and the information to be generated and held on those products by each of the food businesses that physically trade them through the distribution chains. It is specific to the distribution for human consumption of marine-captured finfish and their products, from catch through to retailers or caterers.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	
24	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 12877:2011	Traceability of finfish products — Specification on the information to be recorded in farmed finfish distribution chains	farmed finfish, distribution chains	ISO 12877:2011 specifies the information to be recorded in farmed finfish supply chains in order to establish the traceability of products originating from farmed finfish. It specifies how traded fishery products are to be identified, and the information to be generated and held on those products by each of the food businesses that physically trade them through the distribution chains. It is specific to the distribution for human consumption of farmed finfish and their products, from finfish meal, breeding and finfish farming through to retailers or caterers.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	
25	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 12878:2012	Environmental monitoring of the impacts from marine finfish farms on soft bottom	Environmental monitoring, finfish farms	This International Standard establishes an approach for sampling and empirical measurement of soft-bottom impacts from marine finfish net pen farms, and gives examples of detailed procedures for how environmental impacts from finfish net pen farm sites can be monitored in the field, including guidelines for quality assurance of sampling protocols and safety. The emphasis of the environmental impact in this International Standard is on eutrophication effects on the seabed. This International Standard identifies ecological objectives, the indicators used, and the methodology and design, and encompasses guidelines for quality assurance of sampling protocols and operational safety.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	
26	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 16488:2015	Marine finfish farms — Open net cage — Design and operation	finfish farms, open net cage	ISO 16488:2015 presents a general method to be followed for the systematic analysis, design, and evaluation of net cage marine finfish farms. One common style of a net cage finfish farm is shown in Figure 1. A mooring system holds together a series of net cages which contain finfish. Water from the outside environment freely passes through the nets, providing the necessary environment for farming finfish. The methodology presented in this International Standard allows for determination of the adequacy of a given finfish farm's floating structure, nets, and mooring equipment for a given environment. The standard addresses specification of a design basis through evaluation of environmental conditions and acceptable risk, and specifies acceptable techniques for the design and analysis of finfish farms. This International Standard also provides guidelines for development of a handbook which documents procedures for correct maintenance and operation of the finfish farm. The application of the standard is intended to reduce the risk of escape from marine finfish farms. This International Standard is designed to be used by the operator of a net cage marine finfish farm. It is intended that through	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	
27	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 16541:2015	Methods for sea lice surveillance on marine finfish farms	finfish farms, sea lice surveillance	ISO 16541:2015 specifies both a method for sea lice counts on marine finfish farms and a method for sea lice surveillance that can be carried out in any farming area to provide consistent estimates of sea lice infestation. It specifies the best practices associated with monitoring sea lice levels on marine finfish farms for various purposes including the assessment of abundance, prevalence, and treatment efficacy. This will include identifying minimum requirements for specific monitoring program elements (e.g. number of fish and cages to be sampled, frequency of sampling, the level of detail recorded, etc.). It will apply to all marine finfish farms which experience infestation with any of the range of "sea lice" (copepodid) parasites.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	

28	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 16741:2015	Traceability of crustacean products — Specifications on the information to be recorded in farmed crustacean distribution chains	farmed crustacean, traceability, distribution chains	ISO 16741:2015 specifies the information to be recorded in farmed crustacean supply chains in order to establish the traceability of products originating from farm raised crustaceans. It specifies how farmed crustacean products traded are to be identified and the information to be generated and held on those products by each of the food businesses that physically trade them through the distribution chains. It is specific to the distribution for human consumption of crustacean and their products, from farm through to retailers or caterers. The types of business identified in ISO 16741:2015 for farmed crustacean distribution chains are the following: a) farming 1) broodstock collection 2) hatcheries and nurseries 3) crustacean farm 4) harvesting; b) processors; c) traders and wholesalers; d) retailers and caterers; e) logistics including materials brought from other domains; f) feed production.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	
29	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 18537:2015	Traceability of crustacean products — Specifications on the information to be recorded in captured crustacean distribution chains	captured crustacean, traceability, distribution chains	ISO 18537:2015 specifies the information to be recorded in wild-caught crustacean supply chains in order to establish the traceability of products originating from wild-caught crustacean. It specifies how crustacean products traded are to be identified and the information to be generated and held on those products by each of the food businesses that physically trade them through the distribution chains. It is specific to the distribution for human consumption of crustacean and their products, from wild-caught through to retailers or caterers. The types of businesses identified in this International Standard for wild-caught crustacean distribution chains are: - capture operators; - landing businesses and first sale; - processors; - transporters and store operators; - traders and wholesalers; - retailers and caterers; - logistics including materials brought from other domains. Any given crustacean distribution chain may be made up of some or all of the above components but not necessarily in the	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	
30	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 18538:2015	Traceability of molluscan products — Specifications on the information to be recorded in farmed molluscan distribution chains	farmed molluscan, traceability, distribution chains	ISO 18538:2015 specifies the information to be recorded in farmed molluscs supply chains (excluding cephalopods) in order to establish the traceability of products originating from farm-raised molluscs. It specifies how molluscan products traded are to be identified and the information to be generated and held on those products by each of the food businesses that physically trade them through the distribution chains. It is specific to the distribution for human consumption of molluscs and their products from farm through to retailers or caterers.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture	
31	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 18539:2015	Traceability of molluscan products — Specifications on the information to be recorded in captured molluscan distribution chains	captured molluscan, traceability, distribution chains	ISO 18539:2015 specifies the information to be recorded in wild-caught molluscs supply chains in order to establish the traceability of products originating from wild-caught molluscs. It specifies how molluscan products traded are to be identified and the information to be generated and held on those products by each of the food businesses that physically trade them through the distribution chains. It is specific to the distribution for human consumption of molluscs and their products, from wild caught through to retailers or caterers. The types of businesses identified in ISO 18539:2015 for wild-caught molluscan distribution chains are the following: ? capture; ? landing business and first sale; ? depuration and shucking, etc.; ? processors; ? transporters and store operators; ? traders and wholesalers; ? retailers and caterers; ? logistics including materials brought from other domains. Any given molluscan distribution chain can be made up of some or all of the above	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Aquaculture, Consumer protection	
32	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO 22948:2020	Carbon footprint for seafood — Product category rules (CFP-PCR) for finfish	Carbon footprint, finfish	This document specifies requirements for calculating the carbon footprint specific to finfish product category rules (CFP-PCR). This methodology builds on the requirements of International Standards for life cycle assessment (LCA) and products' carbon footprints. This document is applicable to the calculation and communication of finfish products' carbon footprints from fishing and/or cultivation of feed ingredients to the consumption of finfish products. It is applicable to the carbon footprints of products from both fisheries and aquaculture value chains. This document used alone does not apply to specifying a product's overall environmental or sustainability characteristics.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture, Sustainable production	
33	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO/CD 20423	Carbon footprint for seafood — Product category rules (CFP-PCR) for macroalgae	Carbon footprint, macroalgae	This document specifies requirements for calculating the carbon footprint specific to farmed macroalgae product category rules (CFP-PCR). This methodology builds on the requirements of International Standards for life cycle assessment (LCA) and products' carbon footprints. This document is applicable to the calculation and communication of farmed macroalgae products' carbon footprints from seedling cultivation to the consumption of macroalgae products. It is applicable to the carbon footprints of products from aquaculture value chains. This document used alone does not apply to specifying a product's overall environmental or sustainability characteristics.	Under development	Draft	Algae and macroalgae, Sustainable production	
34	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture		ISO/PRF 17273	Waste management and reduction from aquaculture facilities in natural water bodies — Principles and guidelines	Waste management, aquaculture facilities	This document specifies a system for waste management and reduction of solid waste in aquaculture. It includes management plans, methods, principles and guidelines. This document is relevant for aquaculture in marine and fresh water bodies. This document does not apply to land based aquaculture and does not comprise biological waste.	Under development	Draft	Aquaculture	

35	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14046:2014	Environmental management – Water footprint Principles, requirements and guidelines	Life cycle assessment	ISO 14046:2014 specifies principles, requirements and guidelines related to water footprint assessment of products, processes and organizations based on life cycle assessment (LCA). ISO 14046:2014 provides principles, requirements and guidelines for conducting and reporting a water footprint assessment as a stand-alone assessment, or as part of a more comprehensive environmental assessment. Only air and soil emissions that impact water quality are included in the assessment, and not all air and soil emissions are included. The result of a water footprint assessment is a single value or a profile of impact indicator results. Whereas reporting is within the scope of ISO 14046:2014, communication of water footprint results, for example in the form of labels or declarations, is outside the scope of ISO 14046:2014.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
36	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO/TR 14073:2017	Environmental management – Water footprint – Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046	Life cycle assessment	ISO/TR 14073:2017 provides illustrative examples of how to apply ISO 14046, in order to assess the water footprint of products, processes and organizations based on life cycle assessment. The examples are presented to demonstrate particular aspects of the application of ISO 14046 and therefore do not present all of the details of an entire water footprint study report as required by ISO 14046.	Published	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
37	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14040:2006	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework	Life cycle assessment	ISO 14040:2006 describes the principles and framework for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review of the LCA, limitations of the LCA, the relationship between the LCA phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements. ISO 14040:2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies. It does not describe the LCA technique in detail, nor does it specify methodologies for the individual phases of the LCA. The intended application of LCA or LCI results is considered during definition of the goal and scope, but the application itself is outside the scope of this International Standard.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
38	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14040:2006/Amd 1:2020	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework – Amendment 1	Life cycle assessment		Published	Amendment	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
39	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines	Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006 specifies requirements and provides guidelines for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review of the LCA, limitations of the LCA, relationship between the LCA phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements. ISO 14044:2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
40	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006/Amd 1:2017	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines – Amendment 1	Life cycle assessment		Published	Amendment	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
41	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006/Amd 2:2020	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines – Amendment 2	Life cycle assessment		Published	Amendment	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
42	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO/TR 14047:2012	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to impact assessment situations	Life cycle assessment	The purpose of ISO/TR 14047:2012 is to provide examples to illustrate current practice of life cycle impact assessment according to ISO 14044:2006. These examples are only a sample of all possible examples that could satisfy the provisions of ISO 14044. They offer "a way" or "ways" rather than the "unique way" of applying ISO 14044. They reflect the key elements of the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase of the LCA. The examples presented in ISO/TR 14047:2012 are not exclusive and other examples exist to illustrate the methodological issues described.	Published	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
43	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO/TR 14049:2012	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14044 to goal and scope definition and inventory analysis	Life cycle assessment	ISO/TR 14049:2012 provides examples about practices in carrying out a life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) as a means of satisfying certain provisions of ISO 14044:2006. These examples are only a sample of the possible cases satisfying the provisions of ISO 14044. They offer "a way" or "ways" rather than the "unique way" for the application of ISO 14044. These examples reflect only portions of a complete LCI study.	Published	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chain	
44	ISO/TC 207 Environmental management	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO/TS 14071:2014	Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Critical review processes and reviewer competencies: Additional requirements and guidelines to ISO 14044:2006	Life cycle assessment	ISO/TS 14071:2014 provides additional specifications to ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006. It provides requirements and guidelines for conducting a critical review of any type of LCA study and the competencies required for the review. ISO/TS 14071:2014 provides: details of a critical review process, including clarification with regard to ISO 14044:2006; guidelines to deliver the required critical review process, linked to the goal of the life cycle assessment (LCA) and its intended use; content and deliverables of the critical review process; guidelines to improve the consistency, transparency, efficiency and credibility of the critical review process; the required competencies for the reviewer(s) (internal, external and panel member); the required competencies to be represented by the panel as a whole. ISO/TS 14071:2014 does not cover the applications of LCA.	Under development ISO/DIS 14071	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chain	

ISO/TMBG Technical Management Board - groups		ISO 13065:2015	Sustainability criteria for bioenergy		ISO 13065:2015 specifies principles, criteria and indicators for the bioenergy supply chain to facilitate assessment of environmental, social and economic aspects of sustainability. ISO 13065:2015 is applicable to the whole supply chain, parts of a supply chain or a single process in the supply chain. ISO 13065:2015 applies to all forms of bioenergy, irrespective of raw material, geographical location, technology or end use. ISO 13065:2015 does not establish thresholds or limits and does not describe specific bioenergy processes and production methods. Compliance with ISO 13065:2015 does not determine the sustainability of processes or products. ISO 13065:2015 is intended to facilitate comparability of various bioenergy processes or products. It can also be used to facilitate comparability of bioenergy and other energy options.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 16 Horizontal methods for molecular biomarker analysis	ISO 16577:2022	Molecular biomarker analysis Vocabulary for molecular biomarker analytical methods in agriculture and food production		This document defines terms for horizontal methods for molecular biomarker analysis in agriculture and food production.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 16649-2:2001	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs. Horizontal method for the enumeration of beta-glucuronidase-positive Escherichia coli Part 2: Colony-count technique at 44 degrees C using 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl beta-D-glucuronide		This part of ISO 16649 specifies a horizontal method for the enumeration of β -glucuronidase-positive Escherichia coli in products intended for human consumption or for the feeding of animals. It uses a colony-count technique at 44 °C on a solid medium containing a chromogenic ingredient for detection of the enzyme β -glucuronidase. WARNING — Strains of Escherichia coli which do not grow at 44 °C and, in particular, those that are β -glucuronidase negative, such as Escherichia coli O157, will not be detected.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
ISO/TC 238 Solid biofuels		ISO 18134-1:2015	Solid biofuels. Determination of moisture content Part 1: Reference method		This document describes the method of determining the moisture content of a test sample of solid biofuels by drying in an oven and can be used when high precision of the determination of moisture content is necessary. The method described in this document is applicable to all solid biofuels. The moisture content of solid biofuels (as received) is always reported based on the total mass of the test sample (wet basis). NOTE Biomass materials can contain small amounts of volatile organic compounds (VOC) which can evaporate when determining moisture content by oven drying (see References [1] and [2]). The release of such compounds is quite small relative to the overall moisture content as determined by this method and is disregarded in this document.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
ISO/TC 6 Paper, board and pulps		ISO 21437:2020	Pulps Determination of carbohydrate composition		This method describes the determination of the carbohydrate composition in wood pulp samples. This method makes it possible to determine concentrations of individual anhydrous monosaccharides down to 1 mg/g oven-dry pulp.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 21527-2:2008	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds Part 2: Colony count technique in products with water activity less than or equal to 0,95		ISO 21527-2:2008 specifies a horizontal method for the enumeration of viable osmophilic yeasts and xerophilic moulds in products intended for human consumption or feeding of animals, having a water activity less than or equal to 0,95 (dry fruits, cakes, jams, dried meat, salted fish, grains, cereals and cereals products, flours, nuts, spices and condiments, etc.), by means of the colony count technique at $(25 \pm 1) ^\circ\text{C}$. ISO 21527-2:2008 does not apply to dehydrated products with water activity less than or equal to 0,60 (dehydrated cereals, oleaginous, spices, leguminous plants, seeds, powders for instant drinks, dry products for domestic animals, etc.) and does not allow the enumeration of mould spores. Neither the identification of fungal flora nor the examination of foods for mycotoxins lie within the scope of ISO 21527-2:2008. The method specified in ISO 21527-2:2008 is not suitable for enumeration of halophilic xerophilic fungi (i.e. Polypaecilum pisce, Basipetospora halophila) found in dried fish.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 16 Horizontal methods for molecular biomarker analysis	ISO 21569:2005	Foodstuffs Methods of analysis for the detection of genetically modified organisms and derived products Qualitative nucleic acid based methods		ISO 21569:2005 describes the procedure to qualitatively detect genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and derived products by analysing the nucleic acids extracted from the sample under study. The main focus is on polymerase chain reaction (PCR) based amplification methods. It gives general requirements for the specific detection and identification of target nucleic acid sequences (DNA) and for the confirmation of the identity of the amplified DNA sequence. Guidelines, minimum requirements and performance criteria laid down in ISO 21569:2005 are intended to ensure that comparable, accurate and reproducible results are obtained in different laboratories. ISO 21569:2005 has been established for food matrices, but could also be applied to other matrices (e.g. feed and plant samples from the environment). Specific examples of methods are provided in Annexes A to D.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 16 Horizontal methods for molecular biomarker analysis	ISO 21571:2005	Foodstuffs Methods of analysis for the detection of genetically modified organisms and derived products Nucleic acid extraction		ISO 21571:2005 provides general requirements and specific methods for DNA extraction/purification and quantification. These methods are described in Annexes A and B. ISO 21571:2005 has been established for food matrices, but could also be applicable to other matrices, such as grains and feed. It has been designed as an integral part of nucleic-acid-based analytical methods, in particular ISO 21569 on qualitative analytical methods, and ISO 21570 on quantitative analytical methods.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards

53	ISO/TC 308 Chain of custody		ISO 22095:2020	Chain of custody General terminology and models		This document defines a framework for chain of custody by providing: — a consistent generic approach to the design, implementation and management of chains of custody; — harmonized terminology; — general requirements for different chain of custody models; — general guidance on the application of the defined chain of custody models, including initial guidance on the circumstances under which each chain of custody model might be appropriate. This document is applicable to all materials and products. It does not apply to services as final outputs. This document can be used by any organization operating at any step in a supply chain, as well as by standard setting organizations as a reference point for specific chain of custody standards. This document can enhance the transparency of specific claims regarding materials or products and thereby support the reliability of these claims. It is not intended to be used on its own to make or verify such claims. This document is not, on its own, able to	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
54	ISO/TC 34 Food products	ISO/TC 34/SC 4 Cereals and pulses	ISO 5527:2015	Cereals Vocabulary		ISO 5527:2015 defines terms relating to cereals.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
55	ISO/TC 69 Applications of statistical methods	ISO/TC 69/SC 6, Measurement methods and results.	ISO 5725-1:2023	Accuracy (trueness and precision) of measurement methods and results — Part 1: General principles and definitions		This document — introduces conditions, constraints and resources necessary to evaluate a measurement method or a result; — defines an organizational scheme for the acquisition of trueness and precision data by study; — provides the necessary definitions, statistical model and principles for ISO 5725 (all parts). — is not applicable to proficiency testing or production of the reference item that has their own standards (ISO 13528, respectively and ISO Guide 35). This document is concerned exclusively with measurement methods which yield results on a continuous scale and give a single value as the test result, although this single value may be the outcome of a calculation from a set of observations. It defines values which describe, in quantitative terms, the ability of a measurement method to give a true result (trueness) or to replicate a given result (precision). Thus, there is an implication that exactly the identical item is being measured, in exactly the same way, and that the measurement process is under control. This document may be applied to a very wide	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
56	ISO/TC 69 Applications of statistical methods	ISO/TC 69/SC 6, Measurement methods and results.	ISO 5725-2:2019	Accuracy (trueness and precision) of measurement methods and results Part 2: Basic method for the determination of repeatability and reproducibility of a standard measurement method		This document — amplifies the general principles for designing experiments for the numerical estimation of the precision of measurement methods by means of a collaborative interlaboratory experiment; — provides a detailed practical description of the basic method for routine use in estimating the precision of measurement methods; — provides guidance to all personnel concerned with designing, performing or analysing the results of the tests for estimating precision. NOTE Modifications to this basic method for particular purposes are given in other parts of it is concerned exclusively with measurement methods which yield measurements on a continuous scale and give a single value as the test result, although this single value can be the outcome of a calculation from a set of observations. It assumes that in the design and performance of the precision experiment, all the principles as laid down in ISO 5725-1 are observed. The basic method uses the same number of test results in each laboratory, with each laboratory analysing the same levels of test sample; i.e. a balanced uniform-level experiment. The basic	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
57	ISO/TC 147 Water quality	ISO/TC 147/SC 1 Terminology	ISO 6107:2021	Water quality Vocabulary		This document defines terms used in certain fields of water quality characterization.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
58	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information technology	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29 Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information	ISO/IEC 23092-2:2020	Information technology Genomic information representation Part 2: Coding of genomic information		This document provides specifications for the representation of the following types of genomic information: — unaligned sequencing reads including read identifiers and quality values; — aligned sequencing reads including read identifiers and quality values; — reference sequences.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards
59	ISO/TC 212 Medical laboratories and in vitro diagnostic systems		ISO 17822:2020	In vitro diagnostic test systems Nucleic acid amplification-based examination procedures for detection and identification of microbial pathogens Laboratory quality practice guide		This document describes the particular clinical laboratory practice requirements to ensure the quality of detection, identification and quantification of microbial pathogens using nucleic acid amplification tests (NAAT). It is intended for use by laboratories that develop, and/or implement and use, or perform NAAT for medical, research or health-related purposes. This document does not apply to the development of in vitro diagnostic (IVD) medical devices by manufacturers. However, it does include verification and validation of such devices and/or the corresponding processes when implemented and used by the laboratories.	Published	Basic standard		Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards

No.	Technical committee (TC)	Standard/Project Reference	Standard Title	Keywords	Abstract/Scope	Status of standard	Standard category	Field of interest
1	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 5009.198-2016	Shellfishes--Test method of domoic acid in amnesic shellfish poisoning	Shellfishes, domoic acid	This Standard specifies enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, liquid chromatography, and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry for the determination of amnesic shellfish poisoning in shellfish. The enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay in this Standard applies to the determination of amnesic shellfish poisoning in shellfish and its products. Liquid chromatography and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry apply to the determination of domoic acid (DA) in amnesic shellfish poisoning in shellfish and its products (excluding salted products). Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
2	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 5009.45-2003	Method for analysis of hygienic standard of fish and other aquatic products	fish, hygienic standard	This standard specifies: seafood and fish health indicators analysis. This standard applies to: seafood and fish health indicators analysis. The limit of detection of histamine to 50mg/kg.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
3	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 19838-2005	Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point (HACCP) system and guidelines for its application to fish and fishery products	HACCP system, fishery products	This standard specifies: aquatic products processing enterprises HACCP system establish, implement and maintain the basic requirements, This standard applies to: aquatic products processing enterprises HACCP system the establishment, implementation and management, also be used as an external validation technical basis.	Published	Basic standard	Management systems for food certification
4	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 20361-2006	Determination of malachite green and gentian violet residues in fishery products. High performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detector	malachite green, gentian violet, fishery products	This standard specifies the malachite green in aquatic products and LMG residues total metabolites, HPLC fluorescence determination of crystal violet crystalline residue of the total metabolites and hidden color purple. This standard applies to the determination of residues of malachite green and crystal violet in aquatic edible part.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
5	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/Z 21702-2008	Code on quality and safety control of fishery products for export	quality, fishery products	This standard specifies the quality and safety of aquatic products export control General, raw materials, processing enterprises, production and management personnel, production and processing, packaging, storage, transport, product traceability and recall. The main export of aquatic products processing and quality control standards and other safety requirements. The technical guidance document applies to the export of aquatic products quality and safety control.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
6	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.11-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes -- Part 11: Determination of amino acids content in muscle	germplasm, cultured fishes, amino acids	This standard specifies the reagents and materials mainly amino acids in fish muscle determination, instruments and equipment, sampling, analysis procedures and results of the determination. This section applies to the determination of amino acids in fish muscle in the main. Not available for the determination of tryptophan content.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
7	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.13-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes -- Part 13: Analysis of isozyme electrophoresis	germplasm, cultured fishes, isozyme electrophoresis	This standard specifies the reagents and materials fish isozymes polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis analysis of the level, instruments and equipment, sampling, analysis procedures and results of the determination. This section applies to fish in isoenzyme electrophoresis analysis.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
8	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.14-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes - Part 14: Determination of DNA content in somatic cell	germplasm, cultured fishes, DNA content	This standard specifies the reagents and materials fish DNA (DNA) content determination, instruments and equipment, sampling, analysis procedures and results of the determination. This section applies to common freshwater, marine fish.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
9	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.15-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes. Part 15: RAPD analysis	germplasm, cultured fishes, RAPD analysis	This standard specifies the reagents and materials fish RAPD analysis, instruments and equipment, sampling, analysis procedures and results of the determination. This section applies to common freshwater, marine fish.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
10	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.2-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes -- Part 2: Sampling method	germplasm, cultured fishes, sampling	This standard provides a common tool farmed fish germplasm test sample, equipment and supplies, sampling methods, sample size, transportation and preservation. This section applies to farmed fish germplasm sample test sample.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
11	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.12-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes -- Part 12: Method for the Karyotype analysis	germplasm, cultured fishes, Karyotype analysis	This standard specifies the principles of fish karyotype analysis, instruments and equipment, slide specimen preparation and karyotype analysis reagents and materials. This section applies to farmed fish karyotype analysis, for natural populations of fish and other aquatic animals may also refer to the implementation.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
12	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.1-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes -- Part 1: Inspection rule	germplasm, cultured fishes, inspection	This standard specifies the classification of farmed fish germplasm testing, test items contained in the various examinations, determination and review criteria of the test results. This section applies to farmed fish germplasm testing. Natural populations of fish germplasm testing may refer to.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
13	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18654.10-2008	Inspection of germplasm for cultured fishes -- Part 10: Determination on nutrient content of muscle	germplasm, cultured fishes, nutrient content	This standard specifies the determination of nutrients in fish muscle samples, sample processing, measurement methods and results of calculations. This section applies to the determination of fish muscle nutrients.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture
14	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 22287-2008	Detection of hepatitis A virus in shellfish -- Conventional RT-PCR and real-time fluorescence RT-PCR	hepatitis A virus, shellfish	This standard specifies the hepatitis A virus in shellfish ordinary fluorescent RT-PCR and RT-PCR detection methods. This standard applies to shellfish detect hepatitis A virus nucleic acid.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
15	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 16871-2008	Redlip mullet standard for parent fish and fingerling	Redlip mullet, parent fish	This standard specifies the mullet <i>Liza haematocheila</i> (Temminck et Schlegel) broodstock and fish sources, quality requirements, inspection rules and testing methods and transportation. This standard applies to assessing the quality of broodstock and barracuda species.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
16	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18108-2019	General rules of fresh marine fish	fresh, marine fish	This standard specifies the requirements, test methods, inspection rules, labels, signs, packaging, transportation and storage of fresh sea fish. This standard is applicable to fresh sea fish, chilled sea fish and fresh sea fish that have not been treated, and have not been treated. Fresh sea fish that only go to scales, to head, to internal organs, and without other treatment can also be referred to.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
17	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 27304-2008	Food safety management system -- Requirements for fish and fishery product processing establishments	management system, fishery product	This standard specifies the aquatic products processing enterprises to establish and implement food safety management system specific requirements, including human resources, prerequisite programs, critical process control, inspection and product traceability and withdrawal. This standard with GB/T 22000 to apply aquatic products processing enterprises to establish, implementation and self-evaluation of its food safety management system, also suitable for this type of food production enterprises of food safety management system of external evaluation and certification. When this standard is used for authentication purposes, should be used with GB/T 22000. GB/T 22000 standard correspondence between the See Appendix A.	Published	Basic standard	Management systems for food certification

18	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 22729-2008	Oligopeptides powder of marine fish	marine, fish	This standard specifies the marine fish oligopeptide powder product categories, technical requirements, test methods, inspection rules and labels, packaging, transport and storage. This standard applies to marine fish oligopeptide powder production, inspection and sales.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
19	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 18109-2011	Quick frozen finfish	frozen, finfish	This standard specifies the requirements for frozen fish products, test methods, inspection rules, labeling, packaging, storage and transportation. This standard applies to take the head, to the head, gutted whole or gutted, frozen fish products for human consumption.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
20	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 27988-2011	Code of practice for salted fish	salted fish	This standard specifies the basic requirements of salted fish processing enterprises, processing techniques and operational documents and records requirements. This standard applies to brining, dry salting processed into fish production process.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
21	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 29568-2013	Traceability requirement for agricultural products. Fish and fishery products	Traceability, fishery products	This standard specifies the seafood supply chain traceability system components and traceability information recording requirements. This standard applies to all organizations seafood supply chain traceability system design and implementation.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
22	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 29764-2013	Chemicals -- Fish (Oryzias latipes, d-r Medaka) early life stage toxicity test	Oryzias, latipes, d-rR, toxicity	This standard specifies the medaka fish (d-rR strain medaka, hereinafter referred to as "fish") early life stage toxicity test chemical methods overview Equipment, test preparation, test procedures, quality assurance and quality control, data and reports. This standard applies to testing the toxicity of chemicals to fish early life stages (embryonic development and juvenile growth phase).	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
23	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 30894-2014	Salted fish	Salted fish	This standard specifies the terms and definitions of salted fish, requirements, test methods, inspection rules, marking, packaging, transportation and storage. This standard applies to marine fish as raw material, cleaning, salting, drying and other processes processed into dry or semi-salted fish products, fish As raw salted fish may refer to this standard.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
24	NOT AVAILABLE	GB 5009.261-2016	Determination of neurotoxic shellfish poisons in shellfish for export -- Mouse biology method	neurotoxic, poisons, shellfish	This standard specifies a method for the determination of neurotoxic toxin (NSP) in shellfish. This standard applies to shellfish and products in the detection of neurotoxic toxins (NSP).	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
25	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 34733-2017	Diagnostic protocols for cryptocaryonosis of marine fish	cryptocaryonosis, marine fish	This standard gives the marine fish to stimulate the prevalence of cryptococcosis and the main symptoms, the provisions of marine fish to stimulate the diagnosis of cryptococcosis. Methods and requirements for sample collection and processing, diagnosis, confirmation of pathogens and determination of results. This standard applies to marine fish stimulate cryptococcosis diagnosis, epidemiological investigation, quarantine and monitoring.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
26	NOT AVAILABLE	GB/T 19164-2021	Feed material -- Fish meal	Fish meal	This document specifies the technical requirements, sampling, test methods, inspection rules and labeling, packaging, transportation, storage and preservation of feed raw material fishmeal quality period. This document applies to feed ingredients red fish meal, white fish meal and fish fillet meal.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection
27	NOT AVAILABLE	GB 1886.317-2021	National food safety standard - Food additives - β -Carotene (sourced from Dunaliella)	safety standard, Food additives	This Standard is applicable to take the Dunaliella Salina as the raw materials, and obtain the food additives of β -Carotene (sourced from Dunaliella) through extracting and refining.	Published	Basic standard	Management systems for food certification
28	NOT AVAILABLE	NY/T 1709-2021	Green food, algae and its products	Green food, algae	NOT AVAILABLE	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae
29	NOT AVAILABLE	GB 19643-2016	Hygienic standard for marine algae and algae products	Hygienic standard, algae	This Standard is applicable to the edible algae and algae products.	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae

No.	Technical committee (TC)	Standard/Project Reference	Standard Title	Keywords	Abstract/Scope	Status of standard	Standard category	Field of interest
1	NOT AVAILABLE	AS/NZS 1766.3.5:1999	Food microbiology - Examination of specific products - Molluscs, crustaceans and fish, and products thereof	microbiology, examination	NOT AVAILABLE	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology
2	NOT AVAILABLE	AS/NZS 1766.2.12:2002	Food microbiology - Examination for specific organisms - Escherichia coli in bivalve molluscs - Rapid method	microbiology, Escherichia coli	NOT AVAILABLE	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology

Annex B

No.	Technical committee (TC)	Standard/Project Reference	Standard Title	Keywords	Abstract/Scope	Status of standard	Standard category	Field of interest	Remarks	Name of partner
1	CEN/WS ClimeFish	CWA 17518:2020	Good practice recommendations for making Climate Adaptation Plans for fisheries and aquaculture	Climate Adaptation Plans, fisheries, aquaculture	This document provides recommendations for good practice for developing effective climate adaptation plans (CAPs) for production systems within the following sectors: marine wild capture fisheries, marine aquaculture, and lake and pond fisheries and aquaculture. NOTE The guidelines are in line with existing literature and adaptation tools on creating adaptation strategies and plans (e.g. FAO, 2019; Barange et al, 2018; ISO 14090, 2019; Brugère & De Young, 2015; Shelton, 2014; EC 2013, Glick, Stein & Edelson, 2011; Grafton, 2010; FAO, 2010; FAO, 2003).	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture, Sustainable production		LVA; HOLOS
2	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	CEN/TR 17559:2022	Algae and algae products - Food and feed applications: General overview of limits, procedures and analytical methods	algae products, analytical methods	This document describes product specifications, product characteristics and other relevant information for algae and algae products for food, nutraceutical and animal feed applications. This document is a general overview of available limits, procedures and analytical methods applicable to algae and algae products used for food and feed applications. This document does not apply to pharmaceutical, cosmetics, fertilizer/biostimulants, chemical and biofuel applications.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection		AWI ; LVA; CTAQUA
3	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17480:2021	Algae and algae products - Methods for the determination of productivity of algae growth sites	algae products, algae growth sites, productivity	This document specifies the methods to be used for the determination of productivity of algae growth sites. This document excludes methods for sampling, harvesting and pre-/postprocessing. Excluded as well is "wild growth", which is defined as algae growing in nature without human interference except when harvesting the algae.	Published	Basic standard	Sustainable production		AWI; CTAQUA
4	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17605:2022	Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Sample treatment	algae products, Sample treatment	This document specifies the sample preparation of dry and wet samples of algae and algae products. This document enables laboratories analysing algae samples to report accurate dry weight percentages and to obtain representative samples possible for further examination.	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae		AWI
5	CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods	EN ISO 4833-1:2013	Microbiology of the food chain. Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms. Part 1: Colony count at 30 degrees C by the pour plate technique (ISO 4833-1:2013)	food chain, colony count	This part of ISO 4833 specifies a horizontal method for enumeration of microorganisms that are able to grow and form colonies in a solid medium after aerobic incubation at 30 °C. The method is applicable to: a) products intended for human consumption and for animal feed; b) environmental samples in the area of food and feed production and handling. This part of ISO 4833 is applicable to: 1) products that require a reliable count when a low limit of detection is specified (below 102/g or 102/ml for liquid samples or below 103/g for solid samples); 2) products expected to contain spreading colonies that obscure colonies of other organisms, e.g. milk and milk products likely to contain spreading Bacillus spp. The applicability of this part of ISO 4833 to the examination of certain fermented food and animal feeds is limited and other media or incubation conditions can be more appropriate. However, this method can be applied to such products even though it is possible that the predominant microorganisms in those products are not detected effectively. For some matrices, the method specified in this part of ISO 4833 can give different results to those obtained using the method specified in ISO 4833-2.	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards	CTAQUA
6	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17399:2020	Algae and algae products - Terms and definitions	algae products, Terms and definitions	This document defines the terms related to functions, products, and properties of algae and algae products. In order to better pack the methodologies, algae are regarded as a functional group of organisms consisting of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes.	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae		CTAQUA
7	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17477:2021	Algae and algae products - Identification of the biomass of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes - Detection and identification with morphological and/or molecular methods	biomass, microalgae, macroalgae	This document specifies a method for the detection and identification of microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes by using morphological methods and/or molecular methods. The morphological methods in this document are applicable to harvested wet biomass and to harvested dried unground biomass from microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes that have been grown and/or harvested for further processing and/or use. The molecular methods in this document are applicable to harvested wet biomass and to harvested dried and/or ground biomass from microalgae, macroalgae, cyanobacteria and Labyrinthulomycetes that have been grown and/or harvested for further processing and/or use. This document describes a toolbox, consisting of several identification methods that can be chosen according to the applicability and purpose of the identification: - morphological methods based on observation and referring to scientific literature on taxonomy; - macroscopic identification; - light microscopic identification; - molecular methods for sequencing and blasting of sequences; - 16S rDNA sequencing; - 18S rDNA sequencing; - rbcL DNA sequencing; - ITS sequencing; - COX1 gene sequencing; - tufA gene sequencing. This document does not deal with genetic purity of the biomass or quantification of the identified taxa. This document is not suitable for the analysis of highly processed biomass with highly degraded DNA where the fragments' length are not sufficient for amplification of the targets and the identification. This document specifies the methods to be used for the measurement of energy content and main elements balances of algae from cultivation or from wild growth and algae products to provide biomass, intended for renewable algal raw material used as bioenergy and in bio-based products. This document does not apply to methods of algae and algae products sampling, harvesting and pre-/postprocessing. This document does not apply to algae and algae products intended for the food and feed sector.	Published	Basic standard	Biomass		CTAQUA
8	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	FprEN 17983	Algae and algae products - Measurement for renewable algal raw material for energy and non-energy applications	renewable algal, energy	This document specifies the methods to be used for the measurement of energy content and main elements balances of algae from cultivation or from wild growth and algae products to provide biomass, intended for renewable algal raw material used as bioenergy and in bio-based products. This document does not apply to methods of algae and algae products sampling, harvesting and pre-/postprocessing. This document does not apply to algae and algae products intended for the food and feed sector.	Under Approval	Basic standard	Sustainable production		CTAQUA
9	CEN/TC 327 Animal feeding stuffs - Methods of sampling and analysis	EN ISO 6498:2012	Animal feeding stuffs - Guidelines for sample preparation (ISO 6498:2012)	feeding stuffs, sample	This International Standard specifies guidelines for the preparation of test samples from laboratory samples of animal feeding stuffs, including pet foods. NOTE 1 The guidelines mostly derive from those developed by AAFCO (see Reference [7]). The guidelines are overruled by special instructions and regulations for sample preparation demanded by specific analysis methods. NOTE 2 Such analysis methods are developed by ISO and CEN. NOTE 3 This International Standard does not include special guidelines for sample preparation for microbiological analysis of microorganisms like yeasts, bacteria and moulds. Nonetheless, for microorganisms which are used as feed additives (probiotics), some important aspects of sample preparation are addressed.	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	Is in the normative references or in the bibliography of CEN/TC 454 standards	CTAQUA
10	CEN/TC 454 Algae and algae products	EN 17908:2023	Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Determination of total lipids content using the Ryckebosch-Foubert method	algae products, analysis, total lipids content	This document specifies a laboratory method for the determination of the total lipid content in micro- and macroalgae by the Ryckebosch-Foubert method.	Published	Basic standard	Algae and macroalgae		CTAQUA
11	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14046:2014	Environmental management Water footprint Principles, requirements and guidelines	Life cycle assessment	ISO 14046:2014 specifies principles, requirements and guidelines related to water footprint assessment of products, processes and organizations based on life cycle assessment (LCA). ISO 14046:2014 provides principles, requirements and guidelines for conducting and reporting a water footprint assessment as a stand-alone assessment, or as part of a more comprehensive environmental assessment. Only air and soil emissions that impact water quality are included in the assessment, and not all air and soil emissions are included. The result of a water footprint assessment is a single value or a profile of impact indicator results. Whereas reporting is within the scope of ISO 14046:2014, communication of water footprint results, for example in the form of labels or declarations, is outside the scope of ISO 14046:2014.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chains		HOLOS, LVA

12	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO/TR 14073:2017	Environmental management — Water footprint — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046	Life cycle assessment	ISO/TR 14073:2017 provides illustrative examples of how to apply ISO 14046, in order to assess the water footprint of products, processes and organizations based on life cycle assessment. The examples are presented to demonstrate particular aspects of the application of ISO 14046 and therefore do not present all of the details of an entire water footprint study report as required by ISO 14046.	Published	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chains		HOLOS, LVA
13	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14040:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework	Life cycle assessment	ISO 14040:2006 describes the principles and framework for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review of the LCA, limitations of the LCA, the relationship between the LCA phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements. ISO 14040:2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies. It does not describe the LCA technique in detail, nor does it specify methodologies for the individual phases of the LCA. The intended application of LCA or LCI results is considered during definition of the goal and scope, but the application itself is outside the scope of this international Standard.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chains		HOLOS
14	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14040:2006/Amd 1:2020	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework — Amendment 1	Life cycle assessment		Published	Amendment	Life cycle assessment in food chains		HOLOS
15	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines	Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006 specifies requirements and provides guidelines for life cycle assessment (LCA) including: definition of the goal and scope of the LCA, the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase, the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase, the life cycle interpretation phase, reporting and critical review of the LCA, limitations of the LCA, relationship between the LCA phases, and conditions for use of value choices and optional elements. ISO 14044:2006 covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies.	Published (Confirmed)	Basic standard	Life cycle assessment in food chains		HOLOS
16	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006/Amd 1:2017	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 1	Life cycle assessment		Published	Amendment	Life cycle assessment in food chains		HOLOS
17	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment	ISO 14044:2006/Amd 2:2020	Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines — Amendment 2	Life cycle assessment		Published	Amendment	Life cycle assessment in food chains		HOLOS
18	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO 22000:2018	Food safety management systems — Requirements for any organization in the food chain	Food safety management systems, food chain	This document specifies requirements for a food safety management system (FSMS) to enable an organization that is directly or indirectly involved in the food chain: a) to plan, implement, operate, maintain and update a FSMS providing products and services that are safe, in accordance with their intended use; b) to demonstrate compliance with applicable statutory and regulatory food safety requirements; c) to evaluate and assess mutually agreed customer food safety requirements and to demonstrate conformity with them; d) to effectively communicate food safety issues to interested parties within the food chain; e) to ensure that the organization conforms to its stated food safety policy; f) to demonstrate conformity to relevant interested parties; g) to seek certification or registration of its FSMS by an external organization, or make a self-assessment or self-declaration of conformity to this document. All requirements of this document are generic and are intended to be applicable to all organizations in the food chain, regardless of size and complexity. Organizations that are directly or indirectly involved include, but are not limited to, feed producers, animal food producers, harvesters of wild plants and animals, farmers, producers of ingredients, food manufacturers, retailers, and organizations providing food services, catering services, cleaning and sanitation services, transportation, storage and distribution services, suppliers of equipment, cleaning and disinfectants, packaging materials and other	Published	Basic standard	Management systems for food certification		LVA, CTAQUA
19	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-1:2009	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 1: Food manufacturing	food safety, food manufacturing	ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRP) to assist in controlling food safety hazards. ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, which are involved in the manufacturing step of the food chain and wish to implement PRP in such a way as to address the requirements specified in ISO 22000:2005, Clause 7. ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain. Food manufacturing operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 apply to an individual establishment or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures implemented, these need to be justified and documented by a hazard analysis, as described in ISO 22000:2005, 7.4. Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of the organization to comply with these requirements. Examples of such exclusions include the additional aspects relevant to manufacturing operations listed under 1), 2), 3), 4), and 5) below. ISO/TS 22002-1:2009 specifies detailed requirements to be specifically considered in relation to ISO 22000:2005, 7.2.3: a) construction and layout of buildings and associated utilities; b) layout of premises, including workspace and employee facilities; c) supplies of air, water, energy, and other utilities; d) supporting services, including waste and sewage disposal; e) suitability of equipment and its accessibility for cleaning, maintenance and preventive maintenance; f) management of purchased materials; g) measures for the prevention of cross-	Published. Under development ISO/CD 22002-1	Basic standard	Consumer protection		LVA
20	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-2:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 2: Catering	food safety, catering	ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 specifies the requirements for the design, implementation, and maintenance of prerequisite programmes (PRPs) to assist in controlling food safety hazards in catering. ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 is applicable to all organizations which are involved in the processing, preparation, distribution, transport, and serving of food and meals and wish to implement PRPs in accordance with the requirements specified in ISO 22000:2005, 7.2. The scope of ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 includes catering, air catering, railway catering, banquets, among others, in central and satellite units, school and industry dining rooms, hospitals and healthcare facilities, hotels, restaurants, coffee shops, food services, and food stores. Users of catering can belong to vulnerable groups, such as children, elderly and/or ill people. In some countries, the term "food services" is used synonymously with catering. The application of ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 does not exempt the user from compliance with current and applicable legislation. Where local legal requirements are in specified for parameters (temperatures, among others) given in ISO/TS 22002-2:2013, the local requirements shall be used by the food business. Catering operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 apply to an individual establishment or process. Although the use of ISO/TS 22002-2:2013 is not mandatory for complying with the requirements in ISO 22000:2005, 7.2, there is a requirement for deviations (exclusions made or alternative measures	Published. Under development ISO/CD 22002-2	Basic standard	Consumer protection		LVA

21	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-3:2011	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 3: Farming	food safety, farming	ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 specifies requirements and guidelines for the design, implementation, and documentation of prerequisite programmes (PRPs) that maintain a hygienic environment and assist in controlling food safety hazards in the food chain. ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 is applicable to all organizations (including individual farms or groups of farms), regardless of size or complexity, which are involved in farming steps of the food chain and wish to implement PRPs in accordance with ISO 22000:2005, 7.2. If an organization is using ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 as a reference for the purpose of making a self-declaration of conformity with or seeking certification to ISO 22000:2005, deviations therefrom (i.e. where exclusions are made or alternative measures are implemented) need to be justified and documented. It is expected that such deviations will not affect the ability of the organization to comply with the requirements of ISO 22000. ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 is applicable to the farming of crops (e.g. cereals, fruits, vegetables), living farm animals (e.g. cattle, poultry, pigs, fish) and the handling of their products (e.g. milk, eggs). It is not applicable to activities such as picking of wild fruits, vegetables and mushrooms, fishing, hunting, which are not considered as organized farming activities. All operations related to farming are included in the scope (e.g. sorting, cleaning, packing of unprocessed products, on-farm feed manufacturing, transport within the farm). However, ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 is not applicable to processing activities carried out on farm premises (e.g. heating, smoking, curing, maturing, fermenting, drying, marinating, extraction, extrusion or a combination of those processes). Neither is ISO/TS 22002-3:2011 applicable to products or animals that are being transported to or from the farm. Farming	Published. Under review	Basic standard	Consumer protection	LVA
22	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-4:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 4: Food packaging manufacturing	food safety, food packaging manufacturing	ISO/TS 22002-4:2013 specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) to assist in controlling food safety hazards in the manufacture of food packaging. This Technical Specification is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexities that manufacture food packaging and/or intermediate products. This document specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) for transport and storage in the food chain to assist in controlling food safety hazards. This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, that are involved in transport and storage activities across the food supply chain and that wish to implement PRPs in such a way as to address the requirements specified in ISO 22000. This document is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain or in isolation. In this document, transport and storage is aligned with ISO/TS 22003:2013, Annex A, Category G. This document includes all food and feed products and food packaging and packaging materials. Live animals are excluded from the scope of this document except when intended for direct consumption, e.g. molluscs, crustaceans and live fish.	Published. Under development ISO/CD 22002-4	Basic standard	Consumer protection	LVA, AWI
23	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-5:2019	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 5: Transport and storage	food safety, transport and storage	This document specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) for transport and storage in the food chain to assist in controlling food safety hazards. This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, that are involved in transport and storage activities across the food supply chain and that wish to implement PRPs in such a way as to address the requirements specified in ISO 22000. This document is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain or in isolation. In this document, transport and storage is aligned with ISO/TS 22003:2013, Annex A, Category G. This document includes all food and feed products and food packaging and packaging materials. Live animals are excluded from the scope of this document except when intended for direct consumption, e.g. molluscs, crustaceans and live fish.	Published. Under development ISO/CD 22002-5	Basic standard	Consumer protection	LVA
24	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/TS 22002-6:2016	Prerequisite programmes on food safety — Part 6: Feed and animal food production	food safety, feed and animal food production	ISO/TS 22002-6:2016 specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) to assist in controlling feed safety hazards in feed and animal food and in materials intended for use in the production of feed and animal food. Feed safety hazards in this context relate to attributes that have a potential to affect adversely animal and/or human health. Prerequisite programmes are intended to ensure feed safety and to prevent, control and detect potential contamination including cross-contamination that could occur under the responsibility of the organization. ISO/TS 22002-6:2016 is applicable to all organizations regardless of size, location or complexity that are involved in the manufacturing and/or supply of feed and animal food and wish to implement a PRP. Feed and animal food operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in this Technical Specification necessarily apply to an individual organization or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures are implemented, these need to be justified by a hazard assessment and verified to be effective. Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of an organization to comply with other requirements contained in this Technical Specification.	Published. Under development ISO/CD 22002-6	Basic standard	Consumer protection	LVA
25	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO/DIS 22002-7	Prerequisite programmes on food safety. Part 7: Retail		This document specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRP) to assist in controlling food safety hazards. This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, which are involved in the retail step of the food chain and wish to implement PRP in such a way as to address the requirements specified in ISO 22000:2018, Clause 8. This document is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain. Food retail operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in this document apply to an individual establishment or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures implemented, these need to be justified and documented by a hazard analysis, as described in ISO 22000:2018, 8.5.2. Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of the organization to comply with these requirements. Examples of such exclusions include the additional aspects relevant to manufacturing operations listed under 1), 2), 3), 4), and 5) below. This document specifies detailed requirements to be specifically considered in relation to ISO 22000:2018, 8.2.4: to be discussed in conjunction with doc 100 a) construction and layout of buildings and associated utilities; b) layout of premises, including workspace and employee facilities; c) supplies of air, water, energy and other utilities; d) supporting services, including waste and sewage disposal; e) suitability of equipment and its accessibility for cleaning, maintenance and preventive maintenance; f) management of purchased materials; g) measures for the prevention of cross-contamination; h) cleaning and sanitation; i) ISO 22005:2007 gives the principles and specifies the basic requirements for the design and implementation of a feed and food traceability system. It can be applied by an organization operating at any step in the feed and food chain. It is intended to be flexible enough to allow feed organizations and food organizations to achieve identified objectives. The traceability system is a technical tool to assist an organization to conform with its defined objectives, and is applicable when necessary to determine the history or location of a product or its relevant	Under development	Basic standard	Consumer protection	LVA
26	ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Management systems for food safety	ISO 22005:2007	Traceability in the feed and food chain — General principles and basic requirements for system design and implementation	Traceability, system design, implementation	ISO 22005:2007 gives the principles and specifies the basic requirements for the design and implementation of a feed and food traceability system. It can be applied by an organization operating at any step in the feed and food chain. It is intended to be flexible enough to allow feed organizations and food organizations to achieve identified objectives. The traceability system is a technical tool to assist an organization to conform with its defined objectives, and is applicable when necessary to determine the history or location of a product or its relevant	Published	Basic standard	Consumer protection	LVA
27	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 6887-3:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products	test samples, microbiology, fish	ISO 6887-3:2017 specifies rules for the preparation of fish and fishery product samples and their suspension for microbiological examination when the samples require a different preparation from the methods described in ISO 6887-1. ISO 6887-1 defines the general rules for the preparation of the initial suspension and dilutions for microbiological examination. ISO 6887-3:2017 includes special procedures for sampling raw molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms from primary production areas. NOTE 1 Sampling of raw molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms from primary production areas is included in this document, rather than ISO 13307, which specifies rules for sampling from the terrestrial primary production stage. ISO 6887-3:2017 excludes preparation of samples for both enumeration and detection test methods where preparation details are specified in the relevant International Standards (e.g. ISO/TS 15216-1 and ISO/TS 15216-2 for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus in food using real-time RT-PCR). ISO 6887-3:2017 is intended to be used in conjunction with ISO 6887-1. It is applicable to the following raw, processed or frozen fish and shellfish and their products (see Annex A for classification of major taxa): a) Raw fishery products, molluscs, tunicates and echinoderms including: - whole fish or fillets, with or without skin and heads, and gutted; - crustaceans, whole or shelled; - cephalopods; - bivalve molluscs;	Published	Basic standard	Microbiology	CTAQUA

28	ISO/TC 34/SC 9 Microbiology	ISO 6887-3:2017/Amd 1:2020	Microbiology of the food chain Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products -	test samples, microbiology, fish		Published	Amendment	Microbiology		CTAQUA
29	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture	ISO/DIS 20423	Carbon footprint for seafood — Product category rules (CFP-PCR) for macroalgae	Carbon footprint, macroalgae	This document specifies requirements for calculating the carbon footprint specific to farmed macroalgae product category rules (CFP-PCR). This methodology builds on the requirements of International Standards for life cycle assessment (LCA) and products' carbon footprints. This document is applicable to the calculation and communication of farmed macroalgae products' carbon footprints from seedling cultivation to the consumption of macroalgae products. It is applicable to the carbon footprints of products from aquaculture value chains. This document used alone does not apply to specifying a product's overall environmental or sustainability characteristics.	Under development	Draft	Algae and macroalgae, Sustainable production		CTAQUA
30	ISO/TC 234 Fisheries and aquaculture	ISO 22948:2020	Carbon footprint for seafood — Product category rules (CFP-PCR) for finfish	Carbon footprint, finfish	This document specifies requirements for calculating the carbon footprint specific to finfish product category rules (CFP-PCR). This methodology builds on the requirements of International Standards for life cycle assessment (LCA) and products' carbon footprints. This document is applicable to the calculation and communication of finfish products' carbon footprints from fishing and/or cultivation of feed ingredients to the consumption of finfish products. It is applicable to the carbon footprints of products from both fisheries and aquaculture value chains. This document used alone does not apply to specifying a product's overall environmental or sustainability characteristics.	Published	Basic standard	Aquaculture, Sustainable production		CTAQUA
31	ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies	ISO 22739:2024	Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies –Vocabulary, provides foundational terms, featuring	Blockchain	This document defines terms relating to blockchain and distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) to clarify the meaning of terms and concepts used in other documents within the domain of ISO/TC 307. Clear, consistent and coherent standards require clear, consistent and coherent terminology. This document follows the rules and guidelines set by ISO/TC 37, Language and terminology, for terminology standards. This document applies to all types of organizations (e.g. commercial enterprises, government agencies and non-profits). The target audience includes but is not limited to academics, solution architects, customers, users, tool developers, regulators, auditors and standards development organizations. This document defines fundamental terminology for blockchain and distributed ledger technologies.	Published	Basic standard	blockchain and distributed ledger technologies		Infoteam S.r.l.
32	ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies	ISO/TS 23635:2022	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies – Guidelines for governance	Blockchain	Due to the fast-evolving nature of DLT systems and their adoption, this document has been developed at a level of abstraction to provide guidance and instruction in diverse contexts. "Distributed ledger technologies" (DLT) includes blockchain technologies. The specific characteristics of blockchain technologies warrant doing so. This document provides guiding principles and a framework for the governance of DLT systems. The document also provides guidance on the fulfillment of governance, including risk and regulatory contexts, that supports the effective, efficient, and acceptable use of DLT systems.	Published	Basic standard	blockchain and distributed ledger technologies		Infoteam S.r.l.
33	ISO/TC 154 Processes, data elements and documents in commerce, industry and administration	ISO/TR 16340:2023	Application of blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food	Blockchain	This document addresses a blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food which realizes continuous and effective tracking of the cold chain food. The following aspects are included: — it explores issues and considerations for cold chain food traceability, especially during the epidemic outbreak; — it describes scenarios and stakeholders for effective tracking of the cold chain food using the platform; — it describes data elements and processes for the platform; — it presents the platform capabilities such as data tamper resistance, sustainability; — it gives relevant use cases based on the platform.	Published	Basic standard	blockchain		Infoteam S.r.l.

Annex C

PLEASE INSERT THE DOCUMENT IN YOUR ORGANISATION'S LETTERHEAD

ANNEX C DECLARATION

Name: _____

Organisation: _____

For the purpose of achieving the objectives as stated in the grant agreement number 101084180-2 concluded by the Partners of the NOVAFOODIES Consortium with the European Commission, the assessment of Standards in the area of environment, fisheries and aquaculture interactions is required.

The National Standardisation Organisation that is Partner of the Consortium, the Romanian National Standards Body – ASRO - will make the required CEN/CLC and ISO/IEC and their own national standards available to the Consortium free of charge upon request.

I am aware that the Standards provided and clearly watermarked “not for distribution outside the NOVAFOODIES Consortium” are not to be used for purposes other than achieving the objectives of the NOVAFOODIES project as set out in the grant agreement and are also not to be shared with individuals other than personnel assigned by my organisation to the NOVAFOODIES project.

I am aware that I must take all necessary steps to comply with the copyright on the standards and standardization documents that I will access free of charge during the project.

Date and Place: _____

Signature: _____

Annex D

Technical quality				Limitation		Consumer protection			Identified gaps
Critical	Average	Good	Additional comments	Interpretation	Discussion	General specification	Sectorial specification	Local/regional use	

Annex E

No	Standard indicative	Standard title	Development organization	Coverage of the domain			Sustainability performance				Technical quality				Limitation		Consumer protection			Identified gaps	
				high	medium	low	LCA - cradle to cradle	LCA - cradle to grave	Product level	Service level	Requirements level	Critical	Average	Good	Additional comments	Interpretation	Discussion	General specification	Sectoral specification		Local/regional use
1	CEN/TR 17559	Algae and algae products - Food and feed applications: General overview of limits, procedures and analytical methods	CEN												General overview	It does not acquire a deep discussion of the topic (general ideas only)	Applicable to any field related to the use of algae (food technology, feed, biomass, etc.)				Slightly poor discussion about sustainability and lack of methods of adaptation for consumption.
2	EN 17399:2020	Algae and algae products - Terms and definitions	CEN												Accurate list of general terms and concepts	Too general topic often not focused in algae-related terms	Many concepts from Biotechnology, but not pointing algae directly.				Precision on the topic (algae vs. other sources)
3	ISO/CD 17648	Quick-frozen coated aquatic products. Specification		LIMITATION FOUND																	

No	Standard indicative	Standard title	Development organization	Coverage of the domain			Sustainability performance				Technical quality				Limitation		Consumer protection			Identified gaps	
				higher	medium	low	LCA - cradle to cradle	LCA - cradle to grave	Product level	Service level	Requirements level	Critical	Average	Good	Additional comments	Interpretation	Discussion	General specification	Sectoral specification		Local/regional use
1	CEN/TR 17559:2022	Algae and algae products - Food and feed applications: General overview of limits, procedures and analytical methods	CEN																		
2	EN 17480:2021	Algae and algae products - Methods for the determination of productivity of algae growth sites	CEN-EN 17605:2022		x				x					x	This document specifies the methods to be used to determine the productivity of algae growth sites.	This document excludes sampling, harvesting and pre-/post-processing methods. Also excluded is "wild growth", which is defined as seaweed growing in nature without human intervention, other than harvesting the seaweed		x		could add geographical location but not use	This document excludes sampling, harvesting and pre-/post-processing methods. Also excluded is "wild growth", which is defined as seaweed growing in nature without human intervention, other than harvesting the seaweed and is not applicable for all seaweeds
3	EN 17605:2022	Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Sample treatment	EN																		
	ISO/TS 22002-4:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 4: Food packaging manufacturing	ISO																		
	ISO/TR 16340:2023	Application of blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food	ISO		x														x		Generic specifications for implement a blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food. Not very deep into seafood sector but generally applicable. Good trail for system architecture design.
	ISO 22739:2020 Status: Withdrawn This standard has been revised by ISO 22739:2024	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies Vocabulary	ISO		x					x				x	This standard contributes to the following FAO Sustainable Development Goal: n. 9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE			x		Generic technical definition about blockchain/DLT, minimal revision from 2020 version.	
	ISO/TS 23635:2022	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies. Guidelines for governance	ISO			x												x	x		Generic specifications for implement a DLT registry, including risk and regulatory contents for the governance.

No	Standard indicative	Standard title	Development organization	Coverage of the domain			Sustainability performance				Technical quality				Limitation		Consumer protection			Identified gaps	
				high	medium	low	LCA - cradle to cradle	LCA - cradle to grave	Product level	Service level	Requirements level	Critical	Average	Good	Additional comments	Interpretation	Discussion	General specification	Sectoral specification		Local/regional use
	EN 17480:2021	Algae and algae products - Methods for the determination of productivity of algae growth sites	EN	x											x	useful (AW)			x		
	EN 17605:2022	Algae and algae products - Methods of sampling and analysis - Sample treatment	EN	x											x	useful (AW)			x		
	ISO/TS 22002-4:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 4: Food packaging manufacturing	ISO		x											not useful for our purposes (AW)	There was no information regarding how to analyse the raw material for food safety. It only states "sufficient data shall be available to enable hazard analysis for food contact" and provides plant based materials as an examples, but does not specify what the appropriate measures would be.				specific information regarding what measures to be taken to ensure food safety when using recycled or plant based materials

No	Standard indicative	Standard title	Development organization	Coverage of the domain			Sustainability performance				Technical quality				Limitation		Consumer protection			Identified gaps	
				higher	medium	low	LCA - cradle to cradle	LCA - cradle to grave	Product level	Service level	Requirements level	Critical	Average	Good	Additional comments	Interpretation	Discussion	General specification	Sectoral specification		Local/regional use
	ISO/TR 16340:2023	Application of blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food			x														x		Generic specifications for implement a blockchain-based traceability platform for cold chain food. Not very deep into seafood sector but generally applicable. Good trail for system architecture design.
	ISO 22739:2020 Status: Withdrawn This standard has been revised by ISO 22739:2024	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies Vocabulary														This standard contributes to the following FAO Sustainable Development Goal: n. 9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE			x		Generic technical definition about blockchain/DLT, minimal revision from 2020 version.
	ISO/TS 23635:2022	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies. Guidelines for governance				x													x	x	Generic specifications for implement a DLT registry, including risk and regulatory contents for the governance.

No	Standard indicative	Standard title	Development organization	Coverage of the domain			Sustainability performance				Technical quality			Limitation		Consumer protection			Identified gaps			
				high	medium	low	LCA-cradle to cradle	LCA-cradle to grave	Product level	Service level	Requirements level	Critical	Average	Good	Additional comments	Interpretation	Discussion	General specification		Sectorial specification	Local/regional use	
1	CWA 17518:2020	Good practice recommendations for making Climate Adaptation Plans for fisheries and aquaculture	CEN		x			x							This can serve as a comparison to developed methods and as guidance to implement all current demands considering sustainability	Can be very useful as guidance for the sustainability approach		x		No mention of IMTA		
2	CEN/TR 17559:2022	Algae and algae products - Food and feed applications: General overview of limits, procedures and analytical methods	CEN	x				x	x						The sustainability aspect is lacking	The Standard can be very useful, as it also outlines the use of algae as novel food.	No mention of other uses of algae (cooling, bio fuel, etc.)		x		No mention of other uses of algae, except food. No information in regards to sustainability of algae.	
11	ISO 14046:2014	Environmental management Water footprint - Principles, requirements and guidelines	EN		x			x	x						General guide for Water Footprint calculation, therefore no specific guidance regarding aquaculture	This document is very important for the consideration of general water footprinting guidelines and the assessment of environmental impacts associated with water use	Discussed approaches can be used for a variety of systems, but the document lacks detailed guidelines (no mention of aquaculture or associated with water use)		x		No mention of IMTAs, overall limitations of the water footprint, no detailed guidelines for aquacultures and innovative procedures	
12	ISO/TR 14073:2017	Environmental management Water footprint - Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046	EN		x			x	x						No mention of aquaculture or related products. Only mentions packaging in a very broad sense.	Match in terms of water sustainability and water footprint calculation, however no specific connections	Could be useful for general overview considering water scarcity footprint		x		fish/algae or aquaculture production should be implemented as an example for the water footprint as this is a very important topic concerning water (degradation)	
18	ISO 23000:2018	Food safety management systems requirements for any organization in the food chain	EN	x				x	x						There is no link made between food safety and circular economy / sustainability.	Useful for every part of the food supply chain - including Novofoodies production sites			x		The greatest problem when making a FSMS work, is to make sure the management and the employees know why and how a company needs a system like that. Helpful would be: "How to explain the importance of a management systems and rules involved to your employees and how to motivate them?" And no link between food safety and circular economy / sustainability (one health approach - critical, ethical and sustainable thinking)	
19	ISO/TS 22002-1:2009	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 1: Food manufacturing	EN				x	x	x						General guide on construction of buildings, handling and movement of workers and products to assure food safety - no specification on fish or algae is made				x		no coverage of environmental topics	
20	ISO/TS 22002-2:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 2: Catering	EN				x	x	x						No mention of specific food groups (for Novofoodies would be fish or algae), general food safety aspects regarding catering services are covered	Matches if Novofoodies final products are offered in catering/ food handling and temperature chains are well described	The focus lies on food safety/consumer protection from foodborne pathogens and cross contaminations - environmental topics are not covered		x		Measures for prevention of malicious contamination are outside the scope of this part of ISO/TS 22002; no coverage of environmental topics	
21	ISO/TS 22002-3:2011	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 3: Farming	EN	x				x	x						Although chapter 7.7 is about about growing, harvesting and handling of aquatic animals, no aquacultures are mentioned, no circular economy/sustainability aspects are mentioned	matches in terms of the focus on farming animals	This standard aims at food safety aspects - sustainability topic is not covered		x		this standard deals with farming, nevertheless aquatic farming is only described superficially, and in no relation with circular economy/sustainability aspects	
22	ISO/TS 22002-4:2013	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 4: Food packaging manufacturing	EN				x	x	x						No mentioning of e.g. waste optimisation or recycling of waste	Relevant for the project in terms of new packaging solutions like land-based seaweed culture for packaging recycled or plant-based materials are already mentioned in the standard.			x		no mention of reusables	
23	ISO/TS 22002-5:2019	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 5: Transport and storage	EN		x			x	x						No mentioning of e.g. waste optimisation or recycling	Matches in terms of transportation and storage of the endproducts			x		no identified gaps	
24	ISO/TS 22002-6:2016	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 6: Feed and animal food production	EN		x			x	x						waste and use of disinfectant/pesticides is never set in context with its impact on the environment; e.g. produce as less waste as possible or recycle/separate wastes correctly; in terms of disinfectants/pesticide etc. maybe a quantum satis like principle would be a good approach - use only as much as needed, but never more	Matches the field of the product when producing feed of aquatic sources.	Is this standard relevant in systems like IMTA, where wastes/byproducts become feed?		x		No information about feed that is produced from residual material in a production site for food e.g. fish meal or if wastes/byproducts from one level, become feed for another (like in systems like IMTA)	
25	ISO/DIS 22002-7	Prerequisite programmes on food safety - Part 7: Retail	EN				x	x	x							Coverage with fish and algae products especially concerning correct storage of products	Not much information in this standard, mostly cross references to ISO 22002:100 which isn't accessible			x		no gaps identified
26	ISO 22005:2007	Traceability in the feed and food chain - General principles and basic requirements for system design and implementation	EN	x				x	x						With an implemented traceability system way to realise circular economy will be a lot easier, but there is no connection made in the standard.	A functioning traceability system is very important for a food and feed supply chain, which is safe for human, also to remain an overview of the products in use and to find the source of any obtaining problems or hazards quickly. This includes fisheries and aquacultures, as well.	The information in the standard is very superficial, implementing a functioning traceability system will take a lot of time and resources. With an implemented traceability system identifying ways to realise circular economy will be a lot easier.		x		There could be more specific guidance in implementing such a system and also a calling how to use the system in a more ecologically sustainable way (ethical and sustainable thinking)	

No	Standard indicative	Standard title	Development organization	Coverage of the domain			Sustainability performance				Technical quality			Limitation		Consumer protection			Identified gaps			
				low	medium	higher	LCA-cradle to cradle	LCA-cradle to grave	Product level	Requirements level	Critical	Average	Good	Additional comments	Interpretation	Discussion	General specification	Sectorial specification		Local/regional use		
1	ISO 14046:2014	Environmental management Water footprint Principles, requirements and guidelines	International Standards Organization												Aquaculture dependant on either land based or offshore, the water management is essential to assess the environmental footprint.						The steps in the assessment are not elaborated. They provide a general idea for the assessment but not the clear picture.	
2	ISO/TR 14073:2017	Environmental management - Water footprint - Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046	International Standards Organization												Sector specific clear examples were provided for water footprint analysis.	Sector specific examples provide clarity in the application of water footprint analysis to assess the environmental impact.					Lack of examples specifically related to aquaculture or algal cultivation	
3	ISO 14040:2006/Amendment 1	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework	International Standards Organization												Generic standard. The specific explanation on how to adopt the steps for different categories were not explained	It is the universal standard framework applied for performing Life Cycle Sustainability assessment in all sectors					problem because lack of explanation for each steps like functional unit, system boundary makes each consumer use their own choice. This poses a problem	
4	ISO 14044:2006/Amendment 2	Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines	International Standards Organization												The requirements are applied for performing Life Cycle Sustainability assessment in all sectors despite its generic nature.	These requirements are applied for performing Life Cycle Sustainability assessment in all sectors despite its generic nature.					problem because lack of explanation for each steps like functional unit, system boundary makes each consumer use their own choice. This poses a problem	
5	CWA 17518:2020	Good practice recommendations for making Climate Adaptation Plans for fisheries and aquaculture	The European Committee for Standardization												Lack of details at each preparatory step.	The recommendation for preparing Climate Adaptation plans	is mostly dependant on wild harvesting. Making adaptation based on climate change from the results of the LCA is crucial to have a sustainable aquaculture systems					processes in Novofoodies involve natural water sources widely influenced by climate change. Hence specific instructions on the application of the requirements in the case

